

Proposal

Submission date
11/05/2022

Status:

Under review

From project: [Tan Tari Bricks](#)

For call for proposals: [iGEM Design League Competition 2022 - Project Proposal](#)

Organized by: [iGEM Design League](#)

Team: [Tan Tári Bricks](#)

Tan Tári Bricks is this year's iDL Chilean Team. We propose a platform based on synthetic and computational biology to evaluate the risk of Antarctic beta-lactamases for developing inhibitory proteins. By focusing on three key areas: a new scientific approach, education for the Chilean people, and taking political action to tackle this problem, we aim to develop an integrated solution in the Chilean territory for the Antimicrobial Resistance problem.

1.1 Project Summary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global health threat that could cause ten million deaths annually in 2050¹. Health Authorities have highlighted that AMR is a complex phenomenon involving human, animal, and environmental factors. Therefore, it demands multidisciplinary approaches to investigate its causes and establish actions to mitigate its impact on different ecosystems².

Recent studies revealed that environmental microbes might be a source of novel resistance mechanisms. Moreover, it has been evidenced that the Antarctic Peninsula soils have remarkable bacterial diversity, hosting microbes showing high resistance to multiple antibiotics and a vast repertoire of resistance genes, including an array of antibiotic inactivation enzymes yet to be characterized³. Beta-lactamases are of particular concern since they degrade beta-lactam antibiotics, one of the most used therapies to combat infections globally. On the other hand, the increase in people's transit from and to the Antarctic Peninsula, mainly through Chile, raises the probability of introducing these resistance genes to South America and the rest of the world. Thus, Antarctic Peninsula soils should be monitored as a potential source of resistance mechanisms that could be transferred to pathogenic bacteria, worsening the AMR crisis. This knowledge is essential to understand these mechanisms and move forward to the development of new molecules to counteract them. As a Chilean team, we feel responsible for taking this knowledge from the southernmost place in the world and leveraging it to design strategies that contribute to stopping AMR.

Our project considers acting from Chile in three key areas to face antimicrobial resistance and the potential threat of Antarctic resistance genes under an integrative view: (1) the development of computational and synthetic biology-based solutions to assess the risk of and develop inhibitors against Antarctic resistance mechanisms; (2) educating Chilean population on antibiotics and the AMR problem; and (3) contacting key stakeholders and promoting political actions oriented to encourage the discussion and legislation on this topic.

Regarding the scientific proposal, we chose the Antarctic beta-lactamases as a case study. Thousands of putative beta-lactamase genes were identified among Antarctic Peninsula soil metagenomes, selecting two from different classes (A and D) to test our design. The risk assessment pipeline uses bioinformatics tools to gather relevant information about these resistance enzymes, including their modeled 3D structure, substrate binding properties, and action spectrum. Also, to predict if they would be sensitive to known inhibitors. Furthermore, our design includes a genetic device to express the beta-lactamases in *E. coli*, and a set of experimental assays to test the bioinformatic predictions and the resistance of bacteria producing these enzymes.

Additionally, we propose a method to develop beta-lactamase inhibitor proteins (BLIPs) with increased effect against Antarctic beta-lactamases. For this aim, we provide methods and two genetic devices for the high throughput fluorescence-based testing of rationally designed inhibitor variants to find those with increased binding affinity for the target beta-lactamase. Also, we provide a device for the scalable production of engineered BLIPs, including an extracellular secretion signal to facilitate and lower the cost of their purification from culture supernatants of *E. coli* cells, and a Trojan Horse uptake domain to facilitate their penetration into the periplasm of the target cell to exert their action. In sum, the four designed devices comprise seventeen new bioparts for the iGEM repository.

Finally, to address the 2030 Agenda of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), different activities and events were made promoting Health and Well-being (SDG3), Quality Education (SDG4), and Gender Equality (SDG5). In this line, we contacted relevant local Authorities and policymakers to discuss about AMR and related bill projects in Chile, the current absence of Chile in the GLASS global AMR surveillance system, and the importance of promoting science-based solutions in our country. Also, teaching activities and outreach communications were created to spread relevant information among the general public, schoolchildren, and undergraduate students. The main topics included science, microbes, Antarctica, synthetic biology, and especially the consequences of antibiotic abuse in Chile and the risks associated with AMR. Furthermore, in every team activity, we ensured the participation of at least 50% of women, especially in the Human Practices events, which also reflects the equity in our team composition, aiming to bridge the gap in the participation of women in science.

References

- 1 Murray C (2022) [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(21\)02724-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(21)02724-0)
- 2 World Health Organization (2021) ISBN 978-92-4-002733-6
- 3 Marcoleta AE (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152003>

1.2 Track

Human Health and Biomedicine

1.3 Promotional Video.

[Try watching this video on www.youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com)

1.4 Project Presentation Video

[Try watching this video on www.youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com)

1.5 Team and Attributions.

Hi! We are Tan Tári Bricks. The following paragraphs will present the team's organization and each member's detailed responsibilities. To achieve our goals, we created three commissions: **1. Content, Design and Communications; 2. General Coordination, Human Practices and Collaborations, and 3. Bioinformatics Development and Experimental Approach.** Team members, mentors and instructors signed up for each commission, each fulfilling a different role detailed below.

Instructors:

The role of the instructors was to give us constant feedback on the work being carried out according to the commission to which they belong and to review the English language of the different writings, in addition to attending the weekly general meetings. Besides, they helped us to contact various people and entities relevant to our project (stakeholders). Thus, Dr. Andrés Marcoleta put us in contact with the Public Health

Institute and a journalist from our University. Dr. Francisco Chávez contacted the pharmaceutical chemist Dr. Carlos Lagos and the artist Alen Lauzan (<https://alen-lauzan.blogspot.com/>) who helped us with some artistic illustrations for the project. Finally, Dr. Julieta Orlando provided us with access to metagenomic data and with a MindTheGraph account for graphic design. The role of the instructors was especially relevant for the Bioinformatics Development and Experimental Approach Commission, where Dr. Andrés Marcoleta guided us regarding the choice of beta-lactamases and the beta-lactamase inhibitor protein for the proof of concept, also he gave a presentation at the iGEM Symposium that we organized. Both, Dr. Chavez and Dr. Marcoleta helped us in designing the plasmid constructs and corrected our protocols for the building and test stage. Furthermore, they helped us to carry out two workshops for school children. Moreover, all of our Instructors' laboratories and computational capabilities were available for any activity related to the project, whether scientific or human practices.

Mentors:

The role of the mentors was key, as they helped us in the execution of specific tasks. For their part, Camilo Berríos and Patricio Arros guided us to 1) Generate the beta-lactamase and BLIP models, 2) Run the molecular dynamics and 3) Run BeatMusic with the beta-lactamase-BLIP complex. Claudio Valenzuela helped us in the generation of images from BioRender for the representation of the protocols of the Build and Test

section. Antonia Ramos, who has excellent skills in the development of audiovisual material, gave us feedback on the audiovisual material generated, lent us her recording equipment and Canva premium account and edited the project trailer video and part of the edition of the project presentation video, in addition she helped us creating animations for both videos. Antonia also allowed us to document the different activities by taking photos of them. Camilo also helped us with recording the project presentation video, creating animations for it and editing the script. Patricio was essential in helping us correct english texts and giving us tips for the audiovisual content of social networks. Ian, for her part, gave us constant feedback on human practices and helped us make a video in the framework of a collaboration with iGEM Biotech EC.

Team members:

The heart of this project is undoubtedly the team members; they were the ones in charge of raising the project and developing it during all these months considering: the problem and solution proposal, generation of audiovisual content, the accomplishment of the different deliverables, designing interviews for the stakeholders, contacting and interviewing them, updating the Gantt chart, performing bioinformatics and computational biology tasks, contacting other iDL teams and establishing collaborations, writing the JOGL, carrying out activities such as the art fair, workshops for school children, the Tan-Tári Open Academy, among others.

All the mentors and instructors, along with invited specialists, participated in the Tan-Tári Team Academy Sessions -where the scientific dimension of the project was discussed- giving us feedback and guidance. In addition, scientific articles were presented by Antonia Ramos and Dr. Andrés Marcoleta. The team members were the nucleus of these sessions, which raised the problems to be solved. Amelia, José, Hugo and Rocío presented scientific articles focused on the problem and the solution like molecular dynamics, beta-lactamase inhibitors proteins articles, screening method, among others, and, finally, the feedback received was used to constantly improve the project.

The following section describes the commissions, considering their members, work axes, and main actions. In addition to the general meetings, each commission had weekly meetings which were attended by the team members and mentors and, only when required, by the instructors. The role of the coordinators was to plan different tasks for the commission during weekly meetings, contribute to the execution of the activities and functions of their commission, and finally, present the progress of their commission at the general meetings.

1. General Coordination, Human Practices and Collaborations

Coordinator: Amelia Cox, Team Leader **Instructors:** Dr. Francisco Chávez and Dr. Andrés Marcoleta. **Mentors:** Ian Pérez.

Team members: Hugo González, Rocío González-Parada y José Coche.

This commission, also referred to as the **Human Practices and Collaborations**, contemplated three axes of work: 1) Human practices, 2) Collaborations, and 3) Medals requirements.

Axis 1: Human practices

For the first axis, *human practices*, we started by mapping the stakeholders. Then, as part of the design thinking methodology, we contacted those selected and conducted interviews and surveys to gather information on the problem's relevance and opinions (interest in the project, feedback, etc.). Thus, the information gathered was used to improve the project:

- To validate or refute assumptions.
- To detect needs or associated unsolved problems.
- Make projections and evaluate perceptions of the project.

Afterward, we continued with the design thinking process, managing with other commissions the activities proposed in this process to link with stakeholders and reshape our project with the information that we were collecting.

Axis 2: Collaborations

Understanding that collaborative work in all areas is essential for developing and improving a project, the second axis of this commission was related to collaborations. We contacted different iGEM-DL teams to fulfill our goal and managed virtual meetings. Something essential to achieve these collaborations was to always be in contact with other team's commissions to detect needs that these alliances could solve.

Axis 3: Medals requirements

Finally, regarding the last axis -the Medals requirements- we ensured that the requirements for the different medals were met and we were attentive to the different deadlines. To this end, we periodically confirmed that the other commissions carried out the necessary tasks to comply with the above, based on a Gantt chart divided by sections, and were also in charge of collecting doubts to deliver them through the Team Leader by Discord.

2. Bioinformatics Development and Experimental Approach

Coordinator: José Coché, Team member. **Instructors:** Dr. Andrés Marcoleta and Dr. Francisco Chávez. **Team members:** Hugo González, Amelia Cox y Rocío González. **Mentors:** Camilo Berríos, Antonia Ramos and Patricio Arros.

This commission contemplated two axes: 1) Computational Biology; and 2) Synthetic Biology.

Axis 1: Computational biology

The first axis included all the bioinformatics analyses selection of two Antarctic beta-lactamases whose risk will be evaluated for designing an optimized beta-lactamase inhibitor protein. For this purpose, bioinformatics programs were used to search for antimicrobial resistance genes from Antarctic soil metagenomes, computational biology tools for protein structural modeling and molecular dynamics for their refinement. In addition, a computational strategy was used for modeling the beta-lactamase and inhibitor protein interaction, and a web platform was used to evaluate the affinity of different randomly generated variants of the inhibitor protein. Finally, a codon optimization algorithm for beta-lactamase sequences and the optimized beta-lactamase inhibitor protein, BLIP-I, was used.

Axis 2: Synthetic Biology

The second axis consisted of designing the genetic circuit to evaluate the spectrum of action of the selected Antarctic beta-lactamases and to assay the inhibitory capacity of the optimized version of the BLIP-protein. For this purpose, a search for standardized parts necessary for developing the genetic circuit was carried out, and the corresponding BioBricks were designed. In addition, the entire methodology was developed to carry out the experimental objectives proposed from the design above.

3. Content, Design and Communications Commission

Coordinator: Rocio González, Team member **Instructors:** Dra. Julieta Orlando. **Team members:** Macarena Gajardo, Amelia Cox, Gabriela Carrasco. **Mentors:** Patricio Arros, Claudio Valenzuela y Antonia Ramos.

This commission was in charge of preparing all the audiovisual content used to spread the Tan-Tári Bricks project. The work plan was divided into four main axes:

Axis 1: Graphic design

This axis was in charge of choosing a palette and a font to standardize the content, facilitate reading and generate a recognizable public identity. Cold colors representing the Southern Ocean and the Antarctic continent were selected. Secondly, a logo was created to represent the project, based on three main elements that summarize the proposal: a beta-lactam antibiotic (the capsule), the Antarctic continent, and a segment of DNA in the center of the main text representing Synthetic Biology. The third mission of this axis was to create a mascot character for the group, a collective representative of every team member. The selected mascot resulted in an ice cube dressed in a white laboratory apron, representing the glaciers of southern Chile and the national scientific community. The mascot's name was Tarito, derived from the Yagán word "Tári," which means cold.

Axis 2: Social Networks

This axis aim consisted in creating and maintaining social networks to archive and communicate all the activities carried out by the team related to the Tan Tári Bricks project. Firstly, the Instagram account @tantaribricks was created as the primary and official communication network. This account was used to introduce the team members, expose the Tan Tári Bricks project objectives to the general public, publicize educational events and contests organized by the team and collaborating teams, and prepare and

share original educational content and scientific capsules in topics related to the project. Secondly, the Twitter account @TanTariBricks was created to be used as a supportive network for the official media described above, and the Youtube channel Tan Tári Bricks as a means for live transmissions and backup for the audiovisual content generated by the project.

Axis 3: Educational Content

Considering that scientific divulgation is one of the main axes of any project linked to the iGEM Design League, this commission created educational content relevant to understand the Tan-Tári Bricks project as a means of outreach and global dissemination in both English and Spanish languages. The educational content was shared as posts on the aforementioned social networks. It included the following topics: The Antarctic continent as a natural laboratory and its relevance for Chile, Climate Change, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Bacteria and Archaea, Antibiotic Resistance, Beta-Lactamases, Genetics, Systems Biology, Synthetic Biology, Bioinformatics and Computational Biology, Public Policies related to antimicrobial resistance and antibiotics use in Chile, and Gender Equality in Chilean science. All the educational content generated by the project will be compiled as an E-Book, which will be online distributed free of charge through our social networks.

Axis 4: Preparation of audiovisual deliverables for the iGEM Design League 2022 competition

As a requirement of the iGEM Design League 2022 competition, four audiovisual deliverables were created to summarize and describe the Tan-Tári Bricks project: Graphical Abstract, Design Roadmap, Project Trailer Video, and Project Presentation Video.

VIDEOS CREDITS

Credits Promotional Video

Director and video editing: Antonia Ramos; **Script:** Camilo Berríos & Amelia Cox; **Narrator voice:** Rocío González-Parada; **Producer:** Tan-Tári Bricks; **Animations:** Antonia Ramos & Amelia Cox; **People in the video (in order of appearance):** Amelia Cox, Andrés Marcoleta & Francisco Chávez. **English subtitles:** Rocío González-Parada & Hugo González **Spanish subtitles:** Hugo González **Portuguese subtitles:** Camilo Berríos.

Videos (without copyright): The images and videos used in this video were taken by our group in place or given by our instructors from their Antarctic mission. Other videos were taken from the copyright free site Canva.com.

Music (without copyright): Motivate me by Mixaund | <https://mixaund.bandcamp.com> Music promoted by <https://www.free-stock-music.com>. The music that we used was from the page <https://www.free-stock-music.com/> which provides music without copyright and says how to cite them, so the song that we used is cited as indicated.

Credits Project Presentation Video

Directors: Camilo Berríos & Antonia Ramos; **Script:** Camilo Berríos, Antonia Ramos & Team members (each team member wrote a section and then each one was adapted to the script); **Producer:** Tan-Tári Bricks; **Director of Photography:** Camilo Berríos & Antonia Ramos; **Animations:** Camilo Berríos, Gabriela Carrasco, Amelia Cox, Hugo

González, Rocío González-Parada & Antonia Ramos. **English subtitles:** Gabriela Carrasco, José Coché & Patricio Arros. **Spanish subtitles:** Hugo González.

Cast (in order of appearance):

- Susana - Antonia Ramos
- Jaime - Ignacio Silva
- Tarito's Voice - Gabriela Carrasco
- Female Scientist - Macarena Gajardo
- Male Scientist - Hugo González
- Guy in Black Shirt - José Coché
- Girl in grey Shirt - Rocío González-Parada
- Girl in white shirt - Amelia Cox
- Girl in striped shirt - Gabriela Carrasco

We want to mention that, considering our need for another supporting actor for Jaime's role, we asked for help from our Faculty friend, Ignacio Silva. He didn't present the project nor did Antonia Ramos, a team mentor. Susana and Jaime were secondary roles that allowed the team members to present the project, it helped with the narrative. Jaime and Susana are characters that refer to students of the Faculty of Sciences of our university.

Stakeholders (in order of appearance):

- Testimony 1 - Ph.D. Rosalba Lagos
- Testimony 2 - Ph.D. Juan Carlos Hormazábal
- Testimony 3 - Ph.D. Carlos Lagos
- Testimony 4 - Ph.D. Yuri Carvajal

People from our activities who appear in silence (in order of appearance): 1. Ph.D. Julieta Orlando - Instructor - in Antarctica; 2. Ph.D. Andrés Marcoleta - Instructor - pictures in the news and from our school workshops; 3. Ph.D. Macarena Varas and Alexis Gaete in a photograph in Antarctica taking soil samples. They are research colleagues of our instructors; 4. Leonardo Álvarez, Samantha García, Alejandra Oyarzo, Natalie Edwards, and Enzo Galliani as speakers in our symposium; 5. Ph.D. Francisco Chávez - Instructor - in our school workshops; 6. High School students as part of our school workshops; 7. Carlos Vidal as one of the professors that gave classes in our Tan-Tári Open Academy.

Images and videos (without copyright): The images and videos used in this video were taken by our group in place or given by our instructors from their Antarctic mission, others were taken from copyright free sites, these were: 1. Canva.com and 2. <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Portada> rel="noopener noreferrer" target="_blank"> <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Portada> rel="noopener noreferrer" target="_blank" style="color: rgb(17, 85, 204);"><https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Portada>. **Music (without copyright):** 1. Epic Cinematic Adventure Music | ICELAND by Alex-Productions | <https://onsound.eu/> Music promoted by <https://www.free-stock-music.com> Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/deed.en_US 2. Music Credit: LAKEY INSPIRED Track Name: "Blue Boi" Music By: LAKEY INSPIRED @ <https://soundcloud.com/lakeyinspired> Original upload HERE - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wAukwLVCvM&t=0s&ab_channel=LAKEYINSPIRED Official "LAKEY INSPIRED" YouTube Channel HERE - <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOmy8wuTpC95lefU5d1dt2Q> License for commercial use: Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported "Share Alike" (CC BY-SA 3.0) License. Full License HERE - <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/legalcode> Music promoted by

NCM <https://goo.gl/fh3rEJ> 3. <https://www.free-stock-music.com/mixaund-motivation-mode.html> 4. <https://www.free-stock-music.com/mixaund-happy-summer.html>

The majority of the music that we used were from the page <https://www.free-stock-music.com/> which provides music without copyright and says how to cite them, so every song that we used is cited as they indicate.

1.6 Graphical Abstract

2.1 Design Roadmap

A journey in iGEM Design League in summary starts with the identification of a local problem and ends with a solution to it, between these two points there is a long road. In this section we are presenting a brief summary of how our journey was. For more details please click the link below where you can find our complete design roadmap. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fJISp0of7M5aLE5XTZ1rcGFQEQ54AhHt/view?usp=sharing>

First, we started with the **problem identification**. Our instructors are experts in the antibiotic resistance problem specifically in the mechanisms developed in Antarctica, so we decided that we would like to help with it. However, we decided that first, we had to study the basic components of this problem and detect the real threats of it. Furthermore, we liked to establish if this was an urgent and local problem to solve. So we carried out preliminary research about it and established the main points. Below you can find the scheme that we made with the main points that we found about this problem and that lead us to face the problem of the Antarctic beta-lactamase and the threat of their transfer to pathogenic bacteria in our country.

Then we did a **stakeholder mapping** in order to choose the most relevant to face our problem. Below you can find a scheme with the stakeholders that were proposed at the beginning and the ones that were chosen.

STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

PROPOSAL

1. CHILEAN GOVERNMENT (AMR PLAN AND ADVANCE TECHNOLOGY RELATED TO ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE)
2. PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE
3. SCIENTISTS
4. NATIONAL PLAN AGAINST ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE
5. MINISTRY OF HEALTH
6. HOSPITALS
7. DOCTORS
8. AGRICULTURAL AND LIVESTOCK SERVICE
9. THE AGRICULTURAL AND LIVESTOCK INDUSTRY
10. IMMUNOSUPPRESSED PEOPLE
11. OLDER ADULTS
12. CONGRESS
13. BOYS, GIRLS AND ADOLESCENTS
14. UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
15. FAO (AMR PLAN FOR ANIMAL HEALTH)
16. NGOS DEDICATED TO HEALTH ISSUES RELATED TO ANTIBIOTICS.

THE CHOSEN ONES

SCIENCE

- SCIENTISTS

PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

- NATIONAL PLAN AGAINST ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE
- PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE
- CONGRESS

STUDENTS

- BOYS, GIRLS AND ADOLESCENTS
- UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Then, we proceed to carry out the **Design thinking methodology** which involves the following steps: i. Empathizing phase, ii. Definition phase, iii. Ideation phase, iv. Prototype phase and v. Test. In the empathizing face **we got in touch with our stakeholders** and also we did **literature research**, this investigation was deeper than the first one that we did in order to establish the problem. Then, in the definition phase, we established our **lines of action based on the information that we collected in the empathizing phase.**

Next, in the ideation phase, we carried out a **brainstorming** in order to make a proposal for **the 3 lines of action that we previously defined.** Below you can find our process of brainstorming for each line of action.

Finally, in the **prototype phase and test phase**, we design the proposals that we previously ideated and then we evaluated them with surveys, in the case of our scientific proposal we only design the proof of concept and how this should be evaluated, considering that several assumptions were previously validated with computational biology.

Below you will find the methodology that we proposed to carry out our synthetic biology-based proposal:

METHODOLOGY

In summary, the steps that we followed to create our project were: 1. Problem identification, 2. Stakeholder Mapping, 3. Design thinking methodology: i. Empathizing phase, ii. Definition phase, iii. Ideation phase, iv. Prototype phase and v. Test. Below you will find a diagram with them.

Furthermore, we would like to mention that the ideation phase, prototype, and test were iterative, as you will see in sections 2.3, 2.4, and in our Design Roadmap document. We look for constant feedback from our stakeholders in order to reshape our project in the different stages of our design thinking process.

Commissions and Timeline: in order to achieve our goals we divided several tasks into commissions and also created a Gantt chart that you can find below.

2.2 Excellence in Biological Engineering Design

Information below.

2.2.1 Standardization.

Our general design, directed to predict and test the fundamental properties of Antarctic beta-lactamases (i.e., structural properties, action spectrum, sensitivity to known inhibitors), and to develop and optimize proteins that inhibit their action, considers the use of four devices comprising different bioparts.

1) Tantari-Bla-discovery device.

The developed device, comprises a BioBrick with two versions (parts IDLBB_0023200 and IDLBB_0023201) including a replaceable Antarctic beta-lactamase gene (*bla* CDS) corresponding to the class-A BKC-like enzyme from *Rhodanobacter* sp. (IDLBB_0023203) or the class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase from *Polaromonas* sp. (IDLBB_0023204), under the control of an Anderson strong constitutive promoter (BBa_J23100), a strong RBS (BBa_J34801) and the *rrmB* terminator (BBa_B0010). Both *bla* CDS were selected for our proof of concept for this instance and are provided as separate parts. Additionally, this biobrick was designed to be assembled on the pSB1C3 backbone compatible with RFC(10) cloning standard, consisting of a pUC19-derived pMB1 replication origin (100-300 copies per cell) and a chloramphenicol resistance marker.

Furthermore, since this device should be suitable to test any environmental beta-lactamase, the Tantari-Bla-discovery backbone (IDLBB_0023202) is provided, in which other *bla* CDS parts can be considered and assembled with the other components of the circuit. As in the case of the selected BKC-like and OXA-like enzymes, the beta-lactamases to be expressed through this device must have their natural signal peptide to reach the periplasm.

Finally, this biobrick was designed to express the Antarctic beta-lactamases in an *E. coli* chassis to test its activity, substrate specificity, and sensibility to known inhibitors, as described in the section 2.2.3.

A

B

Figura 1. A. SBOL representation of the circuit for Antarctic beta-lactamase expression included in the Tantari-Bla-discovery devices. In the two versions of the circuit, the encoded Antarctic beta-lactamase can be either the BKC-like or the OXA-like enzyme. **B.** Map of the device including the plasmid backbone.

2) Tantari-Bla-glow device.

This device was derived from the Mec detective device designed by the iGEM 2019 ASTWS-China team (BBa_K3152018), based on the MecR system found in Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. This system has four parts: *mecR1* (BBa_K3152000), *mecl* repressor (BBa_K3152001), the mec operator (BBa_K3152002), and, downstream of this last element, an mCherry-coding gene (BBa_J06504). It was devised as a biosensor of β -lactam antibiotics optimized for *E. coli* expression, where the binding of these molecules to the MecR1 sensor domain and its subsequent acylation, triggers a conformational change in MecR1 that leads to the degradation of the Mecl repressor and the release of mec operator, resulting in mCherry expression and fluorescence emission.

In the Mec detective biobrick, the β -lactam sensor MecR1 is under the control of the Anderson Strong promoter reverse (BBa_K1463501), a strong RBS (BBa_J34801) and the *rrnB* terminator reverse (BBa_B0020). Also, the Mecl repressor is under the control of the Anderson Medium (BBa_J23110) promoter, a strong RBS (BBa_J34801), and the *rrnB* terminator (BBa_B0010). The mCherry-coding gene is under the control of the mec operator and the same RBS and terminator as Mecl. Additionally, it has been designed to be assembled on the pSB1C3 backbone (pMB1 ori, CmR) compatible with RFC(10) cloning standard.

In our adaptation, the Tantari-Bla-Glow device, we leveraged the high structural similarity found between the sensor domain of MecR (the last 235 amino acids) with the class-A BKC-like and the class-D OXA-like beta-lactamases, modifying the circuit by replacing this domain with the Antarctic *bla* to be characterized, aiming to couple its activity to red fluorescence production in *E. coli*. This way, the device will make possible

fluorescence-based quantitative measurement of the *bla* activity in assays to compare it in the presence of different substrates and inhibitors. This design is the basis for our high throughput screening system to test *bla* inhibitor proteins (BLIPs).

This biobrick has two variants (parts IDLBB_0023205 and IDLBB_0023206) bearing the *mecR-bla* fusion CDS (Antarctic BKC-like or OXA-like *bla*, respectively) and the rest of the circuit components. Furthermore, the mentioned *mecR-bla* fusions are provided as separate parts (IDLBB_0023208 and IDLBB_0023209). Also, since this device should be suitable to test any Antarctic or environmental beta-lactamase, the Tantari-Bla-Glow backbone (IDLBB_0023207) is provided, in which other *bla* CDS parts can be considered and assembled with the other components of the circuit. As in the case of the selected BKC-like and OXA-like enzymes selected for our proof of concept, other beta-lactamases to be expressed through this device must be fused to the *mecR1* transmembrane and cytosolic domains (the first 350 amino acids of MecR1), using only the mature portion of the beta-lactamase (lacking the signal peptide).

Figure 2. *A.* SBOL representation of the main circuits included in the Tantari-Bla-glow device. *B.* Map of the Tantari-Bla-glow device including the plasmid backbone.

3) Tantari-BLIP-profiler device.

Finally, the Tantari-BLIP-profiler device includes a BioBrick (part IDLBB_0023210) bearing an expression cassette including a replaceable gene encoding a beta-lactamase inhibitor protein (BLIP) variant fused to an N-terminal MalE periplasm destination signal (BBa_K3114001), under the control of an Anderson strong constitutive promoter (BBa_J23100), a strong RBS (BBa_J34801) and the *rrnB* terminator (BBa_B0010). Additionally, it comprises a pSB3T5-derived backbone (BBa_K3014006) with a p15A replication origin (low to medium copy number) compatible with Tantari-Bla-discovery and Tantari-Bla-glow, and a tetracycline antibiotic resistance marker. This device was designed to express the different optimized BLIP mutants, designed based on the bioinformatics analyses described in section 2.2.2.6, to evaluate their beta-lactamase inhibitory properties in single strain assays, without the need of BLIP purification. Thus, we also provide the Tantari-BLIP-profiler as a backbone (IDLBB_0023212), ready to assemble the device using other BLIP variants. It is important to consider that if further variants will be expressed from this device, they should also include the periplasmic secretion signal. As a proof of concept, we included in the biobrick the BLIP variant optimized to bind the BKC-like Antarctic beta-lactamase (BLIP*-BKC), which is also provided as a separate part (IDLBB_0023211). The N-terminal periplasm secretion signal allows this protein to reach this cellular compartment and interact with a beta-lactamase produced by the same cell, co-transforming this device with either Tantari-Bla-discovery or Tantari-Bla-glow (more details can be found in section 2.2.3).

A

B

Figure 3. A. SBOL representation of the main circuit included in the Tantati-BLIP profiler device. **B.** Map of the Tantati-BLIP-profiler device including the plasmid backbone.

4) Tantari-BLIP-Trojan device

Comprises a pSB3T5-derived backbone (BBa_K3014006) and a BioBrick (IDLBB_0023213) consisting of an expression cassette including a replaceable gene encoding a beta-lactamase inhibitor protein variant fused to an N-terminal extracellular secretion signal (BBa_K2981006) (to facilitate BLIP purification from extracellular medium) and an optimized C-terminal microcin E492 (MccE492) uptake domain (IDLBB_0023216), under the control of an Anderson strong constitutive promoter (BBa_J23100). Also, this construct includes the *mceC* and *mceJl* genes from the MccE492 production cluster under the control of Anderson Medium constitutive promoters (BBa_J23110). These three genes were also included as a separate part (IDLBB_0023217) to facilitate their use in other circuits. The products of these genes mediate the posttranslational attachment of a salmochelin moiety to the BLIP C-terminus (uptake domain). This modification is recognized specifically by the catechol siderophore receptors FepA, Fiu, and Cir, thus mediating BLIP internalization into the periplasm of the target cells. Thus, the optimized BLIPs expressed from this device are especially appropriate for Gram-negative Bla-producing pathogens harboring these receptors (most *Enterobacteriaceae*). As part of further optimizations, other uptake domains with different target specificity could be tested.

As a proof of concept, the provided biobrick (IDLBB_0023213) comprises the BLIP*-BKC variant optimized to bind the Antarctic class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase, which we propose to use for the Build and Test stage (more details can be found in the section 2.2.3). Also, we provide this beta-lactamase including the signal peptide and the uptake domain as a separate part (IDLBB_0023215). Moreover, to facilitate the assembly of the device using other BLIP variants, we provided the Tantari-BLIP-Trojan device as a backbone (IDLBB_0023214) ready to assemble with other BLIP CDS parts.

A

Tantari-BLIP-Trojan

B

Figure 4. A. SBOL representation of the Tantari-BLIP-trojan main circuit. B. Map of the Tantari-BLIP-trojan device including the plasmid backbone.

All the parts designed in this project are listed in the Table in the following link https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1p7Hv8LsZ2LixCbuAox_a7b5l5RVM-T3lCU_iHjtk-R0/edit#gid=0 . It also includes the Benchling links for each part.

2.2.2 Optimization

2.2.2.1 Antarctic Beta-Lactamases prospection

As starting point, we surveyed putative genes encoding beta-lactamases among eleven previously described Antarctic soil metagenomes (Published by our Team Instructors and Mentors; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152003> and <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147693>). This was done using the RGI software and the CARD database v3.2.3 (June 2022). The identified hits were filtered according to 3 criteria: (1) The hits must correspond to beta-lactamases with carbapenemase activity, (2) share at least 50% of sequence identity with the corresponding gene in the database and, (3) have a length between 50-150% of the genetic sequence in the database. Following these criteria, 130 putative carbapenemases were found in the metagenomic sequences.

Then, the 130 proteins codified in the selected genetic sequences were non-redundantly clustered in 3 consecutive steps: (1) at least 90% of identity and 80% of coverage between all sequences in a cluster, (2) at least 60% of identity and 80% of coverage between all sequences in a cluster and, (3) at least 30% of identity and 80% of coverage between all sequences in a cluster. Steps (1) and (2) were performed using CD-HIT, while step (3) was done using PSI-CD-HIT. The proteins were clustered into 22 distinct groups with centroids as representatives.. The representative proteins of the two most abundant groups were selected as the Antarctic beta-lactamases that would be used for the rest of the project: (1) BKC-beta-lactamase class A and (2) OXA-beta-lactamase class D.

Using Kraken2, we performed taxonomic assignment of the metagenomic contigs containing the beta-lactamase genes identified by RGI, to determine the potential organisms from which the selected beta-lactamases would come. This way, we determined that the class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase comes from *Rhodanobacter sp.* and the class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase from *Polaromonas sp.*

2.2.2.2 Codon Optimization of selected beta-lactamases

Codon optimization of antarctic beta-lactamases was performed for further heterologous expression in *E. coli*. For this, Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) models proposed by Şen *et al.* in 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa248>) were used iteratively. The required single codon and codon pair usage frequencies were obtained from HIVE-CUTs derived from all available GenBank and RefSeq *E. coli* sequences. Codon fitness and Codon Pair Scores (CPS) were calculated from the *E. coli* single codon and codon pair usage frequencies, and then were used as input for the MILP models.

All codon optimization sequence alternatives obtained from running the MILP models iteratively were aligned using MUSCLE v5.0.1428 in diversified mode, then the maximum column confidence multiple sequence alignment (maxcc-MSA) was determined using MUSCLE v5.0.1428. Consensus sequences derived from the maxcc-MSA were obtained using Jalview v2.11.2.5 and then checked using BLASTX to confirm that the nucleotide sequences translated to the corresponding beta-lactamase amino acid sequences. The class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase and the class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase optimized sequences correspond to IDLBB_0023203 and IDLBB_0023204 parts, respectively.

2.2.2.3 Structural Modeling of selected beta-lactamases

The next step involved structural modeling of the selected beta-lactamases using the comparative modeling software Modeller v9.25. Experimentally determined homologous protein templates deposited in PDB were used for both selected beta-lactamases. In particular, for the class-A beta-lactamase, five templates were selected (1BZA, 2CC1, 3BYB, 5A90 and 6W2Z), while for class D, three templates were used (6XJ3, 1K38 and 3IF6). With these templates, 100 structural models were generated for each beta-lactamase and the ten best models were selected according to the DOPE score. These models were uploaded to the Swiss-Model website and the best model was selected according to its QMEAN score.

Structure refinement was done by performing a 100 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation for each beta-lactamase. These MDs were done using GROMACS v2021.5, with input configuration files obtained by analyzing the PDB structures in the CHARMM-GUI server. The predicted signal peptide sequences were cut before MD using PyMOL v2.5.3. Configuration parameters corresponded to solvation in the most optimized water-box containing 0.15 M NaCl, the CHARMM36m forcefield, 310.15K of temperature and any other necessary settings to obtain a NPT system (where mol number, pressure, and temperature are constant). After the MDs were completed, the resulting trajectory and topology files were used as input to calculate the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) values for every frame. The most representative cluster of each protein was selected according to the number of the structures and time intervals when they occur. All of this process was performed with specialized GROMACS modules.

For both proteins, it was observed that there were no major changes in their structural conformation throughout the simulation, corroborating the stability of the modeled structure. As an example, Figure 1A shows the modeled and MD-refined structure for class-A beta-lactamase (representation obtained using PyMOL) and Figure 1B shows

the RMSD over time, which corroborates the stability of the system throughout the simulation. Figures 1C and 1D show the corresponding structure and RMSD over time plot for the class-D beta-lactamase.

Figure 1. Structural representations of selected Antarctic beta-lactamases refined by molecular dynamics. (A) Class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase predicted structure. (B) RMSD over time for the molecular dynamics simulation of the BKC-like beta-lactamase. (C) Class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase predicted structure. (D) RMSD over time for the molecular dynamics simulation of the OXA-like beta-lactamase.

2.2.2.4 Molecular Docking of the selected Antarctic beta-lactamases to beta-lactam antibiotics and known beta-lactamase inhibitors

To characterize the potential enzymatic activity of the Antarctic beta-lactamases and their ligand binding properties, hydrated molecular docking against known carbapenems and beta-lactamase inhibitors was performed using specialized scripts from the ADFR suite v1.1rc1, the Python Meeko package, and Autodock Vina version dbf9226-mod.

For this, proteins and ligands were prepared by incorporating Gasteiger charges, followed by determination of affinity maps for each type of atom present in the protein structure. Next, the most optimal interaction grid of the receptor protein and the interaction map with all possible water molecules that would exist in the native environment were determined.

The final molecular docking step was performed using “500” as the value for the exhaustiveness parameter of Autodock Vina and the ad4 force field of AutoDock 4, followed by the removal of all those water molecules that were displaced by the ligand upon interaction with the protein. Graphical representations of the observed interactions were obtained using PyMOL. All those ligands that stably interacted with the selected beta-lactamases are shown in Table I.

Table I. Ligands that can interact with the beta-lactamases under study according to Hydrated Molecular Docking.

Ligand	Type	Class A Affinity (Kcal/mol)	Class D Affinity (Kcal/mol)
Avibactam	BL-inhibitor	-10.62	-6.19
Meropenem	Carbapenem	-9.282	-7.231
Relebactam	BL-inhibitor	-7.208	-9.339
Sulbactam	BL-inhibitor	-7.68	-8.401
Tazobactam	BL-inhibitor	-3.327	-11.54
Thienamycin	Carbapenem	-5.161	-12.39

As shown in Table I, both proteins would interact with at least two carbapenems, serving as *in silico* evidence of their carbapenemase activity. Also, they stably bond four beta-lactamases inhibitors, which would present some degree of effect against the Antarctic enzymes. According to the relative affinities, the preferred carbapenem for the BKC-like and the OXA-like beta-lactamases are meropenem and thienamycin, respectively. Nevertheless, these predicted ligand binding properties must be tested experimentally, conducting some of the assays described in the section 2.2.3. Figures 2A and 2B, show representative interactions of Antarctic beta-lactamases and ligands obtained using PyMOL.

Figure 2. *Molecular Docking of selected Antarctic beta-lactamases to beta-lactam antibiotics and known beta-lactamase inhibitors. (A) Class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase interacting with relevant ligands. Red: Avibactam, green: Meropenem, blue: Thienamycin. (B) Class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase interacting with relevant ligands. Red: Tazobactam, orange: Relebactam, green: Thienamycin, blue: Meropenem.*

2.2.2.5 Structural modeling of the beta-lactamase/beta-lactamase Inhibitor Protein complex

Next, AlphaFold-Multimer v1.3.0 was used to predict structural models for the interaction between selected beta-lactamases and a beta-lactamase inhibitor protein named BLIP-I from *Streptomyces exfoliatus* (PDB: 3GMV), which was the starting point for the rational design of the beta-lactamase inhibitor proteins sought by our project.

As a complementary strategy, the experimentally determined structure deposited in PDB 3GMW of the class-A TEM-1 beta-lactamase and BLIP-I interaction complex was also used to structurally align the Antarctic BKC-like beta-lactamase and BLIP-I using PyMOL, obtaining a complex of high structural similarity to that obtained by AlphaFold-Multimer, corroborating the predictive reliability of the software and, consequently, of the feasibility of using the complexes initially predicted for both beta-lactamases with BLIP-I for downstream analyses. The interaction models obtained by AlphaFold-Multimer are presented in Figures 3A and 3B.

Figure 3. Structural representation protein complexes formed by selected Antarctic beta-lactamases and beta-lactamase inhibitor protein BLIP-I. (A) Class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase (red) and BLIP-I (blue). (B) Class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase (red) and BLIP-I (blue).

2.2.2.6 *In silico* optimization of BLIP-I to increase its affinity for the Antarctic beta-lactamases

Next, the BeAtMuSiC v1.0 platform was used to perform an iterative *in silico* optimization process of the molecular affinity between beta-lactamases and BLIP-I by site-specific mutagenesis of the latter. For this purpose, 3040 BLIP-I mutations and their effect on the interaction affinity with both beta-lactamases were calculated at each stage. Only mutations that generated a change in binding free energy and occurred at the interaction interface between the two proteins were chosen and the residue in question was replaced in the BLIP-I sequence using PyMOL.

The mutagenesis process was iterated until no new mutations were obtained that generated a difference in binding free energy greater than 0.1 Kcal/mol.

The difference in binding free energy generated by the iterative optimizations of BLIP-I are presented in Tables II and III.

Table II. Iterative *in silico* mutagenesis of BLIP-I to increase its affinity for the Antarctic BKC-like beta-lactamase.

Iteration	Position	Mutation	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{Bind}}$ (Kcal/mol)
1	157	R→F	-1.1
2	73	E→F	-0.87
3	53	D→V	-0.76
4	49	E→Y	-0.36
5	71	R→M	-0.23
6	58	G→C	-0.48
7	40	I→L	-0.18
8	38	G→W	-0.45
9	37	C→W	-0.15
10	43	S→C	-0.15

Table III. Iterative *in silico* mutagenesis of BLIP-I to increase its affinity for the Antarctic OXA-like beta-lactamase.

Iteration	Position	Mutation	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{Bind}}$ (Kcal/mol)
1	157	R→F	-1.11
2	73	E→Y	-0.41
3	1	A→W	-0.33
4	39	V→P	-0.3
5	52	D→P	-0.27
6	39	P→R	-0.15
7	77	K→R	-0.11

As an example of the optimization process output, we generated structural representations of the protein complexes formed by the Antarctic beta-lactamases and the respective optimized versions of BLIP-I including all the suggested mutations (named BLIP*-BKC and BLIP*-OXA), using PyMOL (Figures 4A and 4B). Nevertheless, it is important to note that we designed experimental assays to test a numerous collection of mutants bearing different combinations of the suggested changes, to directly identify the most potent variant *in vivo*, without the need of BLIP purification.

Since for class-A but not for class-D beta-lactamases there is a published crystal structure of a complex with BLIP-I, which shared high structural similarity with the modeled BKC-Bla/BLIP*-BKC complex, thus validating it, we focused on this latter and performed a Molecular Dynamics run to test its stability, according to the method presented in the section "Structural Modeling of selected beta-lactamases". The obtained MD refined structure and the respective RMSD plot over time are presented in Figures 4C and 4D, respectively.

Figure 4. *In silico* optimization of BLIP-I to increase its affinity for selected Antarctic beta-lactamases. (A) Structure of the protein complex formed by Antarctic BKC-like beta-lactamase (red) and BLIP*-BKC (blue). The ten mutations suggested after the *in silico* optimization of BLIP*-BKC are shown in yellow. (B) Structure of the protein complex formed by the Antarctic OXA-like beta-lactamase (red) and BLIP*-OXA (blue). The six mutations suggested after the *in silico* optimization of BLIP*-OXA are shown in yellow. (C) Structural representation of the protein complex formed by the Antarctic

BKC-like beta-lactamase (red) and BLIP-BKC (blue), refined by Molecular Dynamics. (D) RMSD over time for the molecular dynamics simulation of the protein complex formed by the BKC-like beta-lactamase and BLIP*-BKC.*

As shown in the RMSD over time plot presented in Figure 4D, the protein complex formed by class A BKC-beta-lactamase and BLIP-BKC is stable over time and does not present any major structural modifications other than those expected by vibrations or rotations of a protein system in solution.*

It is worth mentioning that the codons of the nucleotide sequence of BLIP*-BKC were optimized according to the method presented in the “Codon Optimization of selected beta-lactamases” section, so that this protein can be heterologously expressed in *E.coli* for the assays intended to test their properties.

According to the evidence obtained from the proof of concept presented in this section, our methodology is suitable to make valuable predictions about relevant properties of the Antarctic beta-lactamases, and allow to design novel variants of inhibitory proteins adapted to Antarctic beta-lactamases. In the following section we will describe a series of experimental assays using a set of genetic devices allowing to test the predicted proteins of the Antarctic beta-lactamases and their inhibitors.

2.2.3 Build and Test

As mentioned previously, our design is directed at learning about the key features of the Antarctic beta-lactamases and their potential to confer resistance to *E. coli* as a model bacterial species comprising pathogenic strains, as well as to develop optimized protein inhibitors against them. We propose the experiments described below to test the predictions made from the computational biology analyses described in the past section

for each of these goals. These assays rely on using the four genetic devices described in section 2.2.1 Standardization.

2.2.3.1 Assays to characterize and evaluate the relative risk of the Antarctic beta-lactamases: assessing their activity, spectrum of action, susceptibility to known inhibitors, and their potential to confer resistance to model bacterial pathogens

We propose the following experimental workflows to evaluate the relative risk and learn about the key features of the Antarctic beta-lactamases. The devices and the experimental pipeline for this goal are outlined in Figure 1.

a) Assays to evaluate the Antarctic beta-lactamase activity and substrate specificity through MIC determinations in microwell plates or using commercial strips

- Transform an *E. coli* chassis (e.g., *E. coli* DH5-alpha) with the Tantari-Bla-discovery plasmid comprising the beta-lactamase to be tested. As a proof of concept, two biobricks are provided to perform these assays, bearing either the class-A BKC-like beta-lactamase from *Rhodanobacter* sp. or the class-D OXA-like beta-lactamase from *Polaromonas* sp. (parts IDLBB_0023200 and IDLBB_0023201, respectively; more details can be found in the section 2.2.1). Both biobricks must be assembled with the pSB1C3 backbone; thus, chloramphenicol must be used to select the cells that incorporated this device. The presence of the transformed plasmid can be further corroborated, for instance, by performing a PCR reaction using primers targeting the plasmid

backbone (flanking the biobrick), and then checking the size of the amplicon obtained by agarose-gel electrophoresis.

- Use the resulting strain to set up bacterial growth assays followed by optical density at 600 nm (OD600) measurements in microwell plates, in presence of different concentrations of a set of beta-lactam antibiotics. Use a microplate reader with temperature control to incubate the plate overnight at 37°C, measuring optical density over time.
- Determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the *E. coli* strain expressing the Antarctic beta-lactamase under study for each antibiotic tested, that is to say, the lowest antibiotic concentration that completely inhibited bacterial growth. As control, use the same *E. coli* chassis transformed with the plasmid backbone (without the biobrick). It is expected that the expression of the Antarctic beta-lactamases will cause an increase in the MIC value for some of the beta-lactam antibiotics predicted to bind the enzyme according to the bioinformatics predictions, compared to the *E. coli* strain that does not express the beta-lactamase. As additional controls, we propose using the Tantari-Bla-discovery plasmid to express in *E. coli* an already characterized class-A and class-D beta-lactamase found in pathogens (e.g., TEM-1 and OXA-48 enzymes), which should confer beta-lactam resistance to the chassis (resembling the known action spectrum for these enzymes). This way, we will address if the Antarctic beta-lactamase has the predicted activity when expressed by a model bacteria, and know its substrate specificity.
- As a complementary approach, the MIC can be determined using commercial MIC strips.
- As possible optimizations to further expand the activity characterization, a C-terminal tag can be added to the Antarctic beta-lactamase to facilitate its purification and perform *in vitro* tests.

b) Assays to evaluate the susceptibility of the Antarctic beta-lactamases to commercial inhibitors

- Transform an *E. coli* host with the Tantari-Bla-discovery plasmid comprising the beta-lactamase to be tested (e.g., the BKC and OXA Antarctic beta-lactamases).
- Use the transformed strain to set up MIC assays in microwell plates (as described in a)), using one or more beta-lactam antibiotics shown to be substrates for the Antarctic beta-lactamase, and also appropriate (recommended) concentrations of known beta-lactamase inhibitors (e.g., tazobactam, avibactam, clavulanic acid, etc.), testing one antibiotic plus one inhibitor at once.
- Determine the MIC for the antibiotic tested of the *E. coli* strain expressing the Antarctic beta-lactamase, comparing what observed in absence or in presence of the inhibitors. In a second round, several concentrations of selected molecules showing some inhibitory effect can be tested. Based on our bioinformatics predictions, we expect that the inhibitors shown to bind the Antarctic beta-lactamases have some degree of inhibitory effect at some concentration in the described assays. This step is very important to establish if the Antarctic beta-lactamases are robustly inhibited or not by some known inhibitor. If not, they will be appropriate candidates for our pipeline to develop novel protein inhibitors against them.

c) Validation of a modified biosensor system for Antarctic beta-lactamase activity characterization and the screening of novel inhibitors

As a complementary method to characterize their activity, and as a cornerstone of the method developed for the high throughput screening and testing of protein inhibitors

optimized to act against Antarctic beta-lactamases, we developed the Tantari-Bla-glow device, coupling beta-lactamase activity with red fluorescence emission. As described in the Standardization section, this device is a modification of the Mec Detective system from the ATWS China iGEM 2019 Team (BBa_K3152018), where the binding of a beta-lactam antibiotic to the periplasmic sensor domain of MecR triggers a signal transduction cascade ending with mCherry expression in the *E. coli* cell transformed with this device. Based on the high structural similarity found between the MecR periplasmic sensor domain and the class-D and class-A serine beta-lactamases, we propose substituting this domain by the mature sequence of an Antarctic beta-lactamase, expecting that the antibiotic binding and inactivation by the fused enzyme will also trigger the signal cascade. Thus, a first step during our test and build phase should be to validate the correct functioning of this device. For the proof of concept, we provide two biobricks including the complete Mec Detective circuit, modified to include the BKC (IDLBB_0023203) or the OXA (IDLBB_0023204) Antarctic beta-lactamases. These bricks must be assembled with the pSB1C3 backbone.

- Transform an *E. coli* host with the Tantari-Bla-glow plasmid encoding the target Antarctic/environmental beta-lactamase fused to MecR, replacing the periplasmic sensor domain. Select transformants using chloramphenicol.
- Use the resulting strain to set up bacterial growth assays in microwell plates (as described in a), using a microplate reader suitable for red fluorescence and OD600 measurements. Select an antibiotic shown to be a good substrate for the Antarctic beta-lactamase and set up wells with different concentrations of this compound.
- Measure red fluorescence emission and OD600 over time while incubating at 37°C with shaking. We expect that antibiotic degradation by the Antarctic beta-lactamase fused to the MecR sensor protein will be correlated with mCherry

expression. Thus, at antibiotic concentrations below the MIC, bacterial growth should be accompanied by red fluorescence emission. The amount of fluorescence produced should be proportional to the activity of the beta-lactamase against the tested antibiotic. This way, we could obtain a quantitative and simple measurement of the relative activity of the beta-lactamase tested, for instance, comparing different antibiotics and the inhibition by different molecules. As a control experiment, we propose fusing to MecR an already characterized class-A and/or class-D beta-lactamase found in pathogens (e.g., TEM-1 and OXA-48 enzymes), incubating the cells comprising the device with a preferred substrate for these enzymes, which should activate red fluorescence emission.

Figure 1. Scheme of the experimental assays to characterize the Antarctic beta-lactamases activity, substrate specificity and sensitivity to known inhibitors using the Tantari-Bla-discovery device. Additionally, an assay to test and validate the Tantari-Bla-glow circuit. Created with Biorender.com.

2.2.3.2 Testing a flexible pipeline to develop, optimize, and produce protein inhibitors against Antarctic beta-lactamases

a) High-throughput testing of a collection of BLIP variants designed through computational analyses

As shown in Section 2.2.2, our bioinformatics design makes possible to obtain a collection of BLIP mutants to be tested, to identify those with increased inhibitory effect against an Antarctic beta-lactamase under study. A major obstacle to test the effectiveness of a numerous set of novel protein inhibitors for beta-lactamases is the requirement to purify them. Thus, we devised a screening protocol to evaluate the inhibitory effect of numerous BLIP variants in single strain assays without the need of BLIP purification. The general idea is to generate an *E. coli* chassis that expresses both the Antarctic beta-lactamase to be tested and one of the BLIP variants, transforming them with both the Tantari-Bla-glow and Tantari-BLIP-profiler devices. As proof of concept, the Tantari-Bla-glow device (IDLBB_0023205) encoding the BKC beta-lactamase (IDLBB_0023203) together with the Tantari-BLIP-profiler (IDLBB_0023210) expressing the BLIP*-BKC (IDLBB_0023211) optimized variant can be used. Given their secretion signals, both proteins should be exported to the periplasm of the same cell, so an auto-inhibitory effect of the beta-lactamase activity should be observed in presence of a certain antibiotic that is substrate of the enzyme. Since the Antarctic beta-lactamase is expressed from the Tantari-Bla-glow device, the inhibitory effect should be inversely proportional to the red fluorescence emission. Thus, several inhibitors (and concentrations) can be tested, searching for those that better quench red fluorescence. To facilitate the assembly of the device with different BLIP variants, we provide Tantari-BLIP-profiler as a backbone (IDLBB_0023212), so it can be directly assembled with CDS parts including other BLIP variants (lacking its extracellular secretion signal) fused

to the N-terminal MalE periplasmic secretion signal. A scheme of the experimental assays and genetic devices for BLIP variants testing is provided in Figure 2.

- Transform an *E. coli* host with the Tantari-Bla-glow plasmid encoding the target Antarctic/environmental beta-lactamase fused to the Mec modified biosensor (replacing the MecR sensor domain). Co-transform the *E. coli* host with a Tantari-BLIP-profiler plasmid encoding one of the candidate optimized BLIP variant designed based on the *in silico* predictions. Select the bacterial cells bearing both plasmids by using the appropriate antibiotics (Cm and Tet).
- Use the resulting strain to set up bacterial growth and beta-lactamase activity assays followed by red fluorescence emission and optical density in microwell plates, using a reader suitable for red fluorescence and OD600 measurements.
- Measure the red fluorescence and optical density over time. We expect that one or more optimized variants (based on bioinformatics predictions), when co-expressed in the same cell than the target Antarctic beta-lactamase, show increased inhibitory effect, quenching the red fluorescence emission. As additional proof to corroborate the specific inhibitory effect of the BLIP variant, a negative control should be performed using an *E. coli* chassis transformed with the device backbone (lacking a BLIP gene). No fluorescence quenching should be observed in this case. As an additional control to validate the assay, a known beta-lactamase/BLIP interacting pair (as that represented by the crystal structure PDB 3GMW) can be used to include in both devices, for instance, Tantari-Bla-glow expressing the TEM-1 beta-lactamase and the Tantari-BLIP-profiler expressing BLIP-I (wild type). In this case, fluorescence quenching should be observed (compared to the situation without inhibitor expression).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the assays and genetic devices proposed to perform a high-throughput testing of different BLIP variants designed based on bioinformatics analyses to increase BLIP affinity to a specific Antarctic beta-lactamase. Created with Biorender.com.

b) Scalable production of the optimized BLIP comprising a Trojan Horse uptake domain

Once identified one or more optimized BLIP variants showing robust inhibitory effect against relevant Antarctic beta-lactamases, we propose a strategy for their scalable production by microbial fermentation using *E. coli* cell factories. For this, the Tantari-

BLIP-Trojan device (IDLBB_0023213) allows the expression of the selected BLIP, fused to an N-terminal extracellular secretion signal. Hence, the produced BLIP can be purified from the culture supernatants without the need for cell lysis and thus avoiding contamination with cytosolic proteins. On the other hand, a major disadvantage of BLIPs is that they cannot easily pass through the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria. To subvert this obstacle, in the Tantari-BLIP-Trojan device the BLIP variant is fused to a C-terminal Microcin E492 Trojan Horse uptake domain (IDLBB_0023216), which mediates protein internalization through the catechol siderophore receptors FepA, Fiu and Cir, allowing BLIP to cross the outer membrane and reach the periplasm of the target cell. For its function, this domain requires the posttranslational attachment of a salmochelin siderophore moiety, which is performed by the concomitant action of the proteins MceJ, MceI, and MceC from the Microcin E492 production cluster. Therefore, a circuit for the expression of these three genes are provided as a separate biobrick (IDLBB_0023217). As a proof of concept, a biobrick including the BLIP*-BKC variant CDS is provided (IDLBB_0023215), which should be assembled with the pSB3T5 backbone.

As possible optimizations, other uptake domains can be explored and tested, for instance, some targeting other bacterial lineages. Additionally, a His tag or similar could be included to further purify the BLIP variant from concentrated supernatants by Nickel-affinity chromatography or similar.

- Transform an *E. coli* chassis suitable for protein expression (e.g., BL21) with the Tantari-BLIP-Trojan device expressing the Antarctic beta-lactamase to be characterized. Select the transformants using tetracycline.
- Grow the cell in M9 minimal medium until a desired DO (this should be optimized to maximize the protein yield). First, growth in flasks can be used to optimize most of the parameters. Then, the culture volume can be scaled up to fit a lab-scale fermentor.

- Optimize a method for BLIP purification from the culture supernatant, for instance, through chromatographic steps.
- The purified BLIP inhibitory effect can be directly tested using the Tantari-Bla-discovery or the Tantari-Bla-glow devices expressing the target beta-lactamase, as described in sections 2.2.3.1 a) and b).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of an *E. coli* chassis transformed with the Tantari-BLIP-Trojan device allowing the expression of an optimized BLIP bearing an N-terminal extracellular secretion signal and an optimized C-terminal microcin E492 uptake domain. MceC protein catalyzes the salmochelin production starting from the enterobactin siderophore produced by most Enterobacteriaceae including *E. coli*. Then, the MceJ/I proteins mediate the posttranslational attachment of the salmochelin moiety to the microcin uptake domain. Additionally, a target cell is shown, where the catechol siderophore receptors FepA, Fiu, and Cir recognize the salmochelin moiety and mediate the internalization of the engineered BLIP into the periplasm (Trojan Horse strategy), where it can exert its beta-lactamase inhibitory function.

2.3 Human Practices

As we mentioned in the Design Roadmap -section 2.1- we contacted different stakeholders for the empathizing and ideation phase for each of our lines of action. The stakeholders contacted, grouped by line of action, the questions and answers that they gave us are as follows.

1) Science with a focus on beta-lactamases

In the case of this line action, we determined that two stakeholders were needed in the scientific category: 1) an expert opinions in the field of chemistry pharmaceuticals field was 2) as well as in the antibiotic resistance considering not only a global focus but also a local one with special attention in the Antarctic reservoir of resistance genes and this person needed to be an authority in order to validated our problem, but also to improve our project, 3) a medical doctor with knowledge about antibiotic resistance and 4) People with who are in charge of surveillance. So, that's why we decided to contact: 1) Pharmaceutical chemist and 2) A scientist from the National Science Academy expert in antibiotic resistance, 3) A medical doctor from a public hospital and 4) National Institute of Health. Furthermore, we wanted, at least, one of them to be a woman, in order to acquire feedback for the development of one of our SDGs: gender equality, specifically in science. We got in touch with them and also designed the interviews. Below you will find what we learn from these activities:

a) Pharmaceutical chemist: Dr. Carlos Lagos

We contacted Dr. Carlos Lagos from San Sebastian University, because of his knowledge in the development of new drugs. He first participated in our ***Tan-Tári Team Academy*** space teaching us the main steps and considerations in the development of new drugs, the types of beta lactams and also molecular dynamics and docking of macromolecules. Before this class we weren't aware of the amount of considerations required in order to design our strategy like: the set temperature of the system has to be

the set to the natural environment temperature in which the living organism that expresses the protein grows, that we have to add ions to the water box for the protein to interact with them, that a system needs to be defined according to Periodic boundary conditions, so the protein does not escape the water box and, that different types of force fields are incompatible between each other.

Initially, as we were going to develop a platform for searching inhibitory molecules from native plants against beta-lactamases, Dr. Lagos explained to us the main considerations when choosing these molecules for pharmaceutical use. After we reshaped our project, and chose to use proteins instead of small molecules -decision that we took based on the literature that says that beta-lactamases got resistant to those small molecules and inspired by the Protera talk in our symposium- Dr. Lagos gave us some tips in order to carry out the dynamics and docking, but now with protein-protein interaction.

Thanks to this we could carry out the molecular dynamics of the beta-lactamases and BLIP that we chose as our models for the proof of concept. Furthermore, this knowledge helped us to do the molecular docking of the more used molecular inhibitors against beta-lactamases.

Furthermore, Dr. Lagos made us note that an important thing to consider is that the drug has to enter the cell, and that's an important challenge. After this, we proceed to discuss it with one of our instructors, Dr. Marcoleta, and that's how the idea of incorporating a signaling domain from the microcine was born.

In another instance, we interviewed Dr. Lagos in order to have his opinion of the development of our strategy considering 1) the problem that we are facing 2) the pharmaceutical scenario -in which he is an expert-, considering that the development of antibiotics is expensive and slow, 3) and our strategy based in synthetic biology.

Among other things, Dr. Carlos Lagos said: "Considering the approach that Tan-Tári Bricks has, which is the development of therapeutic proteins that block these beta-

lactamases that are the proteins that normally appear in antibiotic resistance, we will be able to obtain, for example, an alternative solution, let's say, to the small molecules that are currently used and that could provide in the case of, for example, the BLIP proteins, which are proteins that bind beta-lactamases, a therapeutic alternative, a new product...I think it is an excellent approach”.

Below the link with the complete interview of Dr. Carlos Lagos and the questions that we did:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iaw32_DYH6w&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

Presentation

- Could you please introduce yourself so that those watching this interview will know a little about you?

Category 1. Critical scenario of antibiotic production

- Considering that no new classes of antibiotics have been identified since 1984, how do you see the scenario of antibiotic development in the face of increasing antibiotic resistance and how do you project it 10 to 20 years ahead? What do you think will happen if this is not reversed and we run out of antibiotics in the pharmaceutical chemical sphere?

Category 2. Bioinformatics in strategy and drug development

- What importance do you attribute to the study and application of bioinformatics tools for the development of new strategies and drugs, particularly antimicrobials? What advantages do you see compared to other "classical" techniques or approaches?

Category 3. Beta-lactamases and beta-lactamase inhibitor proteins

- Understanding that beta-lactamases constitute a resistance mechanism that bacteria have generated to resist beta-lactam antibiotics and that their dissemination has been observed in Chile and the world, constituting a serious problem, how necessary do you think it is to study these proteins? What

importance do you attribute to generating new strategies or complementary technologies to antibiotics to address them, such as beta-lactamase inhibitor proteins? Why?

Category 4. Validation of the proposed solution in a scientific and social way

- Given the above, what importance do you attribute, from a scientific and social point of view, to the project developed by Tan-Tári Bricks?

Thanks to this interview, we could validate the following assumptions: 1) The problem we are facing is severe and it affects the whole society, therefore, taking care of it is urgent. 2) New strategies in the pharmaceutical area are needed, antibiotics development is time consuming, slow and expensive. 3) Our synthetic biology based solution is a good approach and our BLIPs could be a new therapeutic alternative and a new pharmaceutical product.

Regarding assumption 2), we would like to mention that this was a key level of the problem to validate, considering that we are developing a solution for it.

Below, a picture of us the day of the interview to Dr. Carlos Lagos

b) Member of the Chilean Academy of Sciences: Dra. Rosalba Lagos

Looking for an expert in antibiotics resistance, we got in touch with Dr. Rosalba Lagos, one of the 6 women members -between 30 men members- of the Chilean Academy of Science and professor of the Faculty of Science at University of Chile and we presented her our project. This was key to reshape our project, because there were some things of our project that, at that point, were not solved like how we could make our BLIPs enter a cell. We told her the idea that we were discussing with our instructors of using a signaling domain from the microcine, as she is an expert in bacteriocins too, she suggested us some articles to learn about this mechanism and to look for evidence related to the biggest protein that has been imported to the periplasmic with this mechanism. Thanks to this, we could add this to our strategy and select the BLIP for our proof of concept based on this evidence related to the importation through siderophores receptors.

We contacted Dr. Rosalba Lagos for a second time, this opportunity was to interview her to validate or refute and reshape our project including different aspects and not only science topics, like the first time. She asked us some questions too to prepare us for the judging sessions.

Among other things, Dr. Rosalba Lagos said: *"There is a natural resistome we must surveil, because this resistome exists in every genetic bacterial cycle. Thus, surveillance is crucial to recognize and study new emerging resistomes so they are not transferred to bacteria that don't have it."*

Also, we would like to highlight that Dr. Rosalba mentioned that to reach gender equality in science -SDG 5 and one of our SDGs- as one of the organizers of a science congress she proposed to have 50% of women as speakers in the conferences. Furthermore, she mentioned that it's important not to withdraw from decision-making spaces and to prioritize those with the greatest impact.

Below you can find the complete interview and the questions that we asked her: [Crisis de Resistencia Antibiótica: Dra. Rosalba Lagos | Tan-Tári Bricks](#)

Presentation

- Could you introduce yourself so that those who see this interview know a little about you?

Category 1. Validation of the problem: Critical scenario of antibiotic resistance

- As a member of the Chilean Academy of Sciences and a researcher focused on antibiotic resistance, could you refer to the importance of scientific research to combat public health problems and, in particular, antibiotic resistance?

Category 2. The chicken or the egg: origin of AMR

- Currently a paradigm has been established in which antibiotic resistance appears as an anthropogenic phenomenon where the exacerbated and negligent consumption of antibiotics seems to be what has led us down this complex and worrying path. However, there is evidence that points to the fact that antibiotic resistance is a mechanism developed by other organisms long before Alexander Flemming revolutionized modern medicine with the discovery of penicillin, what is your vision in this regard, do you think it is important the paradigm that is established with respect to this crisis? How can we contribute to the complementation of both?

Category 3. Gender Equality: how to reach it in science?

- The Tan Tári Bricks team established as one of its transversal axes to work around the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number 5: Gender Equity. In that sense, we would like to know how you see this SDG in the field of scientific research and what those of us who are dedicated to it can do to contribute to this issue.

Category 4. Validation of the proposed solution in a scientific and social way

- Finally, considering that no new classes of antibiotics have been identified since 1984, what importance do you see, from a scientific and social point of view, in the project developed by Tan Tári Bricks?

Thanks to this interview we get valuable information that allowed us to validate the following assumptions 1) The problem of the antibiotic resistance is getting worse everyday 2) The reservoir of resistance genes in the Antarctica could probably arrived Chile and it's necessary to be monitored 3) New strategies to combat them are necessary considering the time and cost associated to the development of new antibiotics 4) A good way to reach gender equality in science is to have 50% of women in activities like conferences, and that's what we did in our Tan-Tári Open Academy and our iGEM Symposium.

We would like to mention that assumptions 2) and 3) were very important to validate as we are affording different stages of the problem: first, monitoring and evaluating the risk of these new antarctic beta-lactamases and second, developing a solution for those which nowadays inhibitors do not work. Furthermore, validating that synthetic biology was a good tool for these two levels of the problem was very necessary too.

c) Doctor Yuri Carvajal, a medical doctor specialized in epidemiology and public health

As medical doctor in charge of the epidemiology section of Van Buren Hospital and with knowledge about antibiotic resistance, we interviewed him with the objective of knowing the perception of the antibiotic resistance problem in the clinical area. He told us, among other things, that this is a serious problem and that it doesn't only begin in hospitals because of antibiotic use, but also for the natural antibiotic resistance

phenomena that occurs in the environment. Among other things, Dr. Yuri Carvajal Md, PhD said:

“The specter of bacteria that has been cultivated in different hospitals shows that antibiotic resistance is an existing phenomenon in our daily life. At the Chilean Institute of National Public Health, we are diagnosing bacteria that are more complex and resistant to antibiotics therefore, we are forced to use more expensive antibiotics”.

Below you can find the link to the complete interview and also the questions that we did related to the line of action of science:

[Crisis de Resistencia Antibiótica: Dr. Yuri Carvajal | Tan-Tári Bricks](#)

Presentation

1. Could you introduce yourself so that those watching this interview know a little about you?

Category 1. Perception of the problem in the clinical area

2. How do you see the scenario of antibiotic resistance today in the clinical setting and how do you project it in another 10-20 years?

3. In your opinion, how prevalent is this problem in Chile?

4. Currently a paradigm has been established in which antibiotic resistance appears as an anthropogenic phenomenon where the exacerbated and negligent consumption of antibiotics seems to be what has led us down this complex and worrying path, however, the evidence points out that antibiotic resistance is a mechanism developed by other organisms long before Alexander Flemming revolutionized modern medicine with the discovery of penicillin, what is your vision in this regard, do you think it is important the paradigm that is established with respect to this crisis? How can we contribute to the complementation of both?

Category 2. The future of this problem in the clinical area

5. What do you think will happen at the clinical level if this crisis is not reversed and we run out of antibiotics?

Category 3. Validation of our synthetic biology solution

7. Considering that no new classes of antibiotics have been identified since 1984, do you think there is room in the clinical world to implement solutions based on synthetic biology such as the one we propose with our project?

This interview helped us to know 1) the visions of medical doctors about this problem and we realized that our solution, apart from being useful for natural environmental beta-lactamases, could also be for the hospital's ones. So, a projection for this project is to study beta-lactamases of these places, but Antarctic beta-lactamases works as a proof of concept. 2) Furthermore, we again validated, but from another point of view -a clinical one-, that the problem that we are facing is urgent, 3) also that our synthetic biology strategy could have space in the clinical area and 4) that new strategies to face antibiotic resistance with lower cost of development that antibiotics are necessary.

Below, a picture of us the day of the interview with Dr. Yuri Carvajal M.D.

d) National Institute of Health (ISP), Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazábal Md, Head of the Infectious Diseases Subdepartment

As the ISP is in charge of antimicrobial resistance surveillance, we visited this place and interviewed Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazábal Md, Head of the Infectious Diseases Subdepartment with the goal of validating two levels of the problem that we are facing: the surveillance and a solution for the beta-lactamases. And also to look for answers for the absence of Chile in GLASS, this is related to our third line of action.

Thanks to this activity, we learned that the surveillance that is being done by the ISP in Chile is more clinical, so the environmental one depends on scientists, until now. So, Dr. Hormazábal said that the surveillance step of our project was so necessary. Furthermore, he told us that new approaches to being developed to face the antibiotic resistance crisis are needed such as our BLIPs, he highlighted that they can't innovate, because they are a reference institution in the country, so they have to followed the standards, so groups like Tan-Tári bricks developing new strategies are necessary.

Dr. Hormazábal said: *"It is very important to create new alternatives to face this crisis, it is the look to the future. We have a global sanitary problem and what is fundamental is that the different research groups have that look to the future to try to formulate new strategies to control the dissemination of resistance...that is the vision that we must have."*

Below you will find the link with the complete interview and also the questions related to our line of action related to science:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3k9-uB1quY4&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

Presentation

1. Could you introduce yourself so that those watching this interview know a little about you.

Category 1: Antimicrobial Resistance in Natural Environments

2. Antimicrobial resistance has traditionally been considered a problem of anthropocentric origin and has been studied in predominantly clinical settings, do you think that studies should be increased and begin to monitor antimicrobial resistance in natural environments? What do you think is its importance?

Category 2: Antimicrobial resistance in extreme natural environments (Antarctica)

3. Along the same lines, given that recent evidence shows that in extreme natural environments (e.g., Antarctica) bacteria have co-evolved their resistance mechanisms to antimicrobials and to substances specific to those sites, what do you think is the importance of studying resistance mechanisms in those places? Why?

Category 3: Validation of the Problem. Beta-lactamases.

4. Beta-lactamases are a resistance mechanism that bacteria have generated to resist beta-lactam antibiotics. In your experience in the ISP, and particularly, according to what you have observed of the dissemination of this type of resistance in Chile (based on the samples that you receive and analyze periodically), how serious or important do you consider this problem? How necessary do you think it is to study these proteins and generate new strategies or technologies to deal with them? Why?

Thanks to this interview we validated that 1) facing two levels of the problem with our project was something good and necessary as Dr. Hormazabal said that environmental surveillance is needed and also creative and innovative solutions to attack new antibiotic resistance strategies. 2) the problem related to the resistome in Antarctica is real and severe, and put Chile in danger. 3) our synthetic biology based solution is a good approach.

Below, some pictures of us at ISP with Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal

2) People's education focused on raising awareness about the correct use of antibiotics

In the case of this line of action, we determined that as school students are part of our stakeholders, we decided that school teachers could lead us to understand the lack of education on antibiotic resistance and the crisis that we are facing, and thus create a school workshop considering what these students know. This person needed to be: a

science teacher with knowledge of the science national curricula in every school grade and someone with knowledge in antibiotic resistance. So, that's why we decided to contact: Javiera Alarcón, a school teacher. Below you will find what we learn from this conversation.

- **Javiera Alarcón school teacher**

Javiera Alarcon is a biology and chemistry school teacher who studied in our University, we got in touch with her in our empathize phase, to ask her whether the resistance to antibiotics topic is included in the school curricula. She told us the following: *“It is in a 7th grade unit, which is when you see microorganisms...but it is not an explicit learning objective”*. Also Javiera suggested us to read the learning objectives of the national school curricula, so we did it and we discovered that the use of antibiotics is addressed indirectly and there is no mention of its responsible use nor the crisis related to them. Below the link with the national school curricula of Science:

<https://www.curriculumnacional.cl/portal/Educacion-General/Ciencias-naturales/>

Thanks to this, we detected that the problem of lack of education is from the beginning: the school. Furthermore, we validated this, when reading the national plan against antimicrobial resistance which says: *“(...) The Ministry of Education will have the objective in the National Plan against AMR to promote that teachers highlight this topic, identifying the opportunities that the national curriculum presents for the achievement of student learning on knowledge against antimicrobial resistance”*. Below the document with this information, important to mention that its application is for 2021-2025 period, i.e is very new.

Link to National Plan against AMR document:

<https://diprece.minsal.cl/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Plan-Nacional-Contra-la-Resistencia-a-los-Antimicrobianos-Chile-2021-2025.pdf>

So, we decided that our choice of doing school workshops was necessary and we took into account the contents about microorganisms that are afford in schools to shape them (more details in 2.4 section).

3) Public policies focusing on integrating Chile to GLASS and the law regarding the labeling of antibiotics

In the empathizing face for this line of action we decided to contact the coordinator of the National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance (RAM): Dr. Tania Herrera, regarding the integration of Chile to GLASS. Because of their answers, in the ideation phase we contacted ISP and, again, because of their answer we contacted the Ministry of Health. In parallel, we contacted Dr. Yuri Carvajal because of his knowledge in public health and resistance to antibiotics. Finally, about the law regarding the labeling of antibiotics, after reading about it and following the process in the empathizing face, in the ideation phase we decided to contact the national congress.

- **Coordinator of the National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance (RAM): Dr. Tania Herrera**

We got in touch by email with Dr. Tania Herrera as the Coordinator of the National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance (RAM) and we told her about our project, she liked it and decided to answer our questions. She said: *"...Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal of the ISP is the person who knows best about international surveillance networks. I hope you find it useful. Tania."* Therefore, in summary, the last word about being part of GLASS is in the ISP hands. Thus, we got in touch with Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal.

Below a picture of the answer that we got from Tania, as emails are private we can not show the message, so we would like to show her email address and that we got an answer.

- **National Institute of Health (ISP), Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazábal Md, Head of the Infectious Diseases Subdepartment**

In the same instance that we interviewed Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal about our project, and all that we mentioned in our first line of action, we also asked him about the National AMR Surveillance Policy and the absence of Chile in GLASS. In summary, Dr. Hormazabal told us that our national surveillance system is quite good for the region in the clinical area, but the surveillance of the environment is something that is not totally covered as it depends on groups like us. Furthermore, he told us that actions are being taken to be part of GLASS, but to hurry this the power of decision is on the Ministry of Health. Below what we asked him (the link of this interview is the same as in our first line of action in section 2.3).

Category 4: National AMR Surveillance Policy

5. The National AMR Surveillance Plan (2022-2026) is an inter ministerial initiative led by the Ministry of Health, which involves the implementation of priority strategies in the country, based on the WHO Global Action Plan. In addition, it proposes an interdisciplinary and multisectoral approach to the problem (from a One Health approach). How do you evaluate the implementation and effects of the Plan, at a general level, and in the areas in which you work? In this evaluation, what aspects do you identify as positive or improvements? What aspects do you identify as obstacles or gaps?

Being aware of the existence of the GLASS system and its scope in terms of standardization of global surveillance:

- What is Chile's current status with respect to GLASS?
- Why do you think that Chile is not currently part of this initiative?
- Do you think it is necessary or relevant for Chile to join GLASS?
- Has the government (Ministry of Health, ISP) considered joining GLASS? If it has not been considered, why not, or if it has been considered, why has it not materialized?
- What is missing or what are the next steps?
- Who should make the decision?
- Who do you think we can approach to express our concerns and suggestions for subscribing to GLASS in particular, and strengthening surveillance systems in general?
- Apart from GLASS, what other important initiatives are being developed in Chile against AMR (Surveillance, Education, Regulation)? Which ones could eventually be of interest for our project?

Thanks to this interview we learned a lot about GLASS and the national situation related to it.

c) Doctor Yuri Carvajal, a medical doctor specialized in epidemiology and public health

In the same instance that we interviewed Dr. Yuri Carvajal about our project, and all that we mentioned in our first line of action, we also asked him about Public Policies regarding antibiotic resistance. In summary, he told us that an ecological vision is needed in the State, that is the only way to develop public policies that could afford the antibiotic resistance problem because it is an ecological one. Below is what we asked him (the link to this interview is the same as in our first line of action in section 2.3).

Category 3. Public Policies

6. From the point of view of public policies, how do you think the problem in question should be addressed at the national level?

Thanks to this we learned and validated that public policies are needed to face this problem and that it has to be with an ecological understanding of the problem in society.

We would like to mention that we did research about the different politics related to the problem of antibiotic resistance in our country. Below the document with the information that we collected:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1uSJZOaYw7nF3vyRejINVh64TES84_eol/view?usp=share_link

2.4. Integrated Human Practices

1) Science with a focus on beta-lactamases

Regarding our first line of action, as we mentioned in 2.3 section, thanks to the feedback that we received in different phases of the Design Thinking Process from Dr. Carlos Lagos, Dr. Rosalba Lagos, Dr. Yuri Carvajal and Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal, we validated and learn from different points of view -clinical, institutional, scientific and pharmaceutical- that:

- 1) The problem we are facing is severe and it affects the whole society, therefore, taking care of it is urgent.
- 2) The reservoir of resistance genes in Antarctica could probably arrive Chile and it's necessary to be monitored.
- 3) The surveillance step of our project is necessary, as in our country it depends until today on scientists interested in this.
- 4) New strategies in the pharmaceutical area are needed, antibiotics development is time-consuming, slow, and expensive.
- 5) Our synthetic biology-based solution is a good approach and our BLIPs could be a new therapeutic alternative and a new pharmaceutical product.

Furthermore, we validated that affording different stages of the problem is necessary and that is possible and accurate with synthetic biology like our project do, these stages are:

- First, monitoring and evaluating the risk of these new antarctic beta-lactamases
- Second, developing a solution for those beta-lactamases which nowadays inhibitors do not work.

Also, as we mentioned in section 2.3, the feedback given by Dr. Carlos Lagos and Dr. Rosalba Lagos helped us to reshape our design. In the case of Dr. Carlos Lagos, we took into account a key thing: the challenge of our BLIPs to enter the cell. And with the information and suggestions that Dra. Rosalba Lagos, we could develop a strategy for our BLIPs to enter the cell including a microcine signaling domain, and consider the BLIP with the lower size based on the evidence of protein with a similar size that has used this strategy. Furthermore, Dr. Carlos Lagos's feedback helped us to carry out our molecular dynamics and our docking, and also to take drug development considerations while running these programs (*in vivo* conditions).

A key component: after we left the idea of the development of a platform of small molecules inhibitors based in native plants because bacteria get resistance to them, as we mentioned in our design roadmap document, the talk of the national biotechnological startup Protera in our iGEM Symposium was a critical thing, considering that thanks to this we got the idea of using proteins against beta-lactamases.

All of these show that our ideation process was an iterative one, where talking with our stakeholders was a critical step to reshaping our strategy and validating assumptions.

2) People's education focused on raising awareness about the correct use of antibiotics

As we mentioned in section 2.3, thanks to the contact with the school teacher and to the research on literature, we detected that the problem of lack of education is from the beginning: the school. So, taking this into account and regarding our second line of action, we developed the following activities in order to raise awareness about the problem we are facing:

School Workshops: we designed and carried out two school workshops. The first one, was the "Scientists in Action" activity of the Explora initiative (Chilean Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation). In this opportunity we supported the participation of a high school from Barrio Yungay in Santiago de Chile. Our Instructor Francisco Chávez was the scientific supervisor of the school.

The work done by the students was closely related to the topic of antibiotic resistance. Their scientific hypothesis was related to differential antibiotic-resistant bacteria in the Mapocho River, the most important in the metropolitan region, in hospital areas and areas with less human presence.

As part of our work, we prepared all the growth media required for their work and were the instructors in all the biosafety measures needed for the microbiological work. The participation of the students was very successful because their work was selected to participate in the Explora National Congress, where schools from all over the country

participate. The students were awarded the most popular work on the project's website in this event. This event allowed us to develop new microbiological learning in the students and to educate them on the importance of the correct use of antibiotics and the global problem of antibiotic resistance.

Below you can find the stats that we got from the survey that we did to the students after the workshop -everything was translated for the JOGL.

We were so happy to contribute with new knowledge as the 100% of the students learned something new, and also to contribute to raising awareness about antibiotic resistance from the beginning as we established in the empathizing phase: school level. The second workshop was focused on microorganisms, antibiotic resistance, and also we talked about our project and the iGEM competition; we used art as a tool for learning, so we carried out an art with microorganisms activity in which the students made the iGEM DL logo with antibiotics and microorganisms (details in 3.6 section).

Tan-Tári Open Academy: Furthermore, we developed the Tan-Tári Open Academy, with the objective to spread not only synthetic biology but also to measure the knowledge about antibiotic resistance of the people who enrolled in these activities and to tell them about our project in the inscriptions forms. All these classes were recorded and published in our YouTube Channel, we made surveys in each session to improve the following one (details in 3.3 section).

iGEM Symposium: We organized a symposium in which we faced different topics, one of them was the antibiotic resistance problem. We presented our project and the local problem that we are facing, we reshape the initial proposal that we had made thanks to advices that iDL staff gave us in online meeting (more details in section 3.3).

Educative capsules: we considered that all the interviews that we did to our stakeholders were so valuable in order to educate people regarding the antibiotic resistance problem and how it affects our country and how projects based on synthetic biology like ours could help to afford it. Therefore, we asked the interviewees if we could make educational capsules with their videos and upload them to YouTube. They allowed us, and now that material is available for everyone. The following link will lead you to the educative playlist that we made in our YouTube channel:

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1hiwC6enbY8&list=PL40OhCskpGTNBlg2vslygPHHNGI7Ec2pP&ab_channel=TanTar)

[v=1hiwC6enbY8&list=PL40OhCskpGTNBlg2vslygPHHNGI7Ec2pP&ab_channel=TanTar](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1hiwC6enbY8&list=PL40OhCskpGTNBlg2vslygPHHNGI7Ec2pP&ab_channel=TanTar)
[iBricks](#)

Educative post: also we made an educational post in which we face concepts related to antibiotic resistance and we improved them by watching the stats of the previous posts. Furthermore, we left a link of interest in our link in bio (details in section 3.3)

3) Public policies focusing on integrating Chile to GLASS and the law regarding the labeling of antibiotics.

Regarding our last line of action, we made the following actions:

Pan-American Health Organization: we sent a document with a description of our project to Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazabal before our visit to the ISP. Thanks to this, we reached something that we couldn't believe: he thought that our project was so good that he sent it to the Pan American Health Organization (OPS).

Publication on the Network of Latin American Public Servants website: as a way of spreading and putting on the Latin American table the antibiotic resistance problem, we got in touch with the **Network of Latin American Public Servants** (Red de Servidores Públicos de América Latina in Spanish) as our Team Leader is part of it. We sent them a summary of our project and they published it on their website and also delivered it in their monthly newsletter. We would like to highlight that this network is composed by

more than 400 Publics Servants from all over Latin America. Below you will find the link to this publication:

https://www.redservidorespublicos.org/product-page/tan-t%C3%A1ri-bricks?utm_source=Red+de+Servidores+P%C3%ABablicos+de+Am%C3%A9rica+Latina&utm_campaign=ffdaacff58-EMAIL_CAMPAIGN_2020_02_10_12_27_COPY_01&utm_medium=email&utm_term=0_96ca6ef553-ffdaacff58-402419406

Ministry of Health: Thanks to the information that we got for our visit to ISP, we got in touch with the Minister of Health, Ximena Aguilera, and with Undersecretary of Public Health Cristóbal Cuadrado in order to promote the incorporation of Chile in GLASS by giving them a letter with our observations. In the beginning, we were cited to assist a meeting on November 4th to discuss this with the Undersecretary and give them the letter we prepared, but this meeting was rearranged to November 9th. As emails are private files, we only attached the fragment that backs up that we had an answer from the Chief of Staff of the Undersecretariat of Public Health, Lican Martínez.

Congress: Thanks to the investigation that we carried out of state of the art regarding antibiotics labeling law (section 2.3), we discussed its weak and missing points. We decided to get in touch with Congress to deliver our observations. Below can be found the email that we sent to the Chief of Staff of Congresswoman Helia Molina, a Deputy of the Chilean Congress. She kindly accepted our request to meet and cited a conversation to give her the letter -this will be on November 11th- with our observations regarding the antibiotics labeling law elaborated by the team.

Educative post: after the research that we made about the state of the art regarding the antibiotics labeling law, we wanted to socialize it with the people, so we made an educational post for our social networks. The link to this post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/Cjq2FJwLVL4/?igshid=NDc0ODY0MjQ=>

2.5 Solving local problems

In 2014, WHO highlighted antimicrobial resistance (AMR) as a serious threat to global health, an exacerbated situation for developing countries. It has been established that one of the leading causes of antimicrobial resistance is the overuse of antibiotics[1].

In developing countries, where the availability of antibiotics over the counter and through unregulated supply chains is widespread [1,2], it facilitates the misuse of antibiotics and, thus, the likelihood of increased AMR.

In addition, miseducation on the subject generates a lack of awareness in the population about the correct use of antibiotics. This is enhanced by the lack or absence of legislation regulating the use of antibiotics to prevent their misuse.

In particular, Chile is one of the countries with the highest consumption of antibiotics in Latin America, having increased by 55% between 1998 and 2015[3].

Beyond the risk posed to developing countries, we must add an extra factor involving Latin America and, mainly Chile, the Antarctic. Recent evidence indicates that Antarctic soils harbor multi-resistant microorganisms to known antibiotics and a great diversity of putative genes that may confer antimicrobial resistance. This includes genes encoding enzymes called beta-lactamases, capable of inactivating the most widely used antibiotics globally, beta-lactams [4].

Given that Chile is the southernmost country in the world and the main gateway to the Antarctic continent, these microorganisms may arrive, either by conventional means of transport or by natural means favored by climate change, to the American continent. This increases the risk of acquiring new resistance mechanisms by human pathogens due to horizontal genetic transfer and their propagation in the Chilean community and eventually to the rest of Latin America.

In the context of global AMR, WHO called on all countries to implement national action plans to address this problem to improve surveillance and strengthen infection prevention and control policies to prevent the impact of antibiotic resistance. Under this scenario, Chile implemented 2017 a National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance with a One Health approach, i.e., a strategy that seeks to increase interdisciplinary collaboration focused on the health of people, animals and the environment. These plans were structured based on the five strategic lines of action established by the WHO Global Action Plan:

However, no plan has been established in Chile for the specific problem that we, Tan-Tári Bricks, intend to address in the context of the AMR crisis: The risk of acquisition of new resistance mechanisms harbored in extreme environments such as Antarctica, by bacterial pathogens.

Taking into account the current context of the problem of antimicrobial resistance and the solutions currently being applied at Tan-Tári, we asked ourselves what impact our project could have on the community and how to evaluate its effect. To answer these questions, we defined the following three objectives:

1) At the scientific level, we have two main objectives. The first corresponds to characterizing and evaluating the risk of beta-lactamase encoding genes present in Antarctic soil metagenomes. With this objective, we seek to contribute to the knowledge of the natural resistomes of extreme environments, facilitating medical and political actions. Indeed, few scientific publications on environment-related antimicrobial resistance were published in Chile, with only 12 out of 97 publications in PubMed

between 2017 and 2020. Based on this knowledge, the other objective corresponds to the design of antimicrobial beta-lactamase inhibitors using the BLIP-I family of beta-lactamase inhibitor proteins as a starting point.

The latter is significant considering that currently, pharmaceutical companies are not developing any new antibiotics and that beta-lactamases encoded in resistance genes can also tolerate the use of current commercial inhibitors. This was validated in the interview we had with the pharmaceutical chemist Carlos Lagos presented in section 2.3, Human Practices.

To evaluate the impact of our scientific proposal on the community, we hope that the knowledge obtained about the risk of Antarctic beta-lactamases will motivate the action of the country's health authorities and the national scientific community. On the other hand, we plan to partner with biotechnology companies dedicated to drug design to expand the use of our Antarctic beta-lactamase inhibitor protein. This implies the positive evaluation of our proposal in controlled clinical trials by national drug regulatory institutions. Thus, we could be prepared as a community for the day when Antarctic antimicrobial resistance genes reach Chilean soil and are transferred to human pathogens.

2) Antibiotic misuse by citizens is a problem that enhances the antimicrobial resistance problem. Therefore, as previously mentioned, the generation of different educational instances for children and teenage students at our University was essential to spread awareness about antibiotic misuse in local communities. To measure the impact of our activities, we implemented surveys to assess initial and subsequent awareness among our audience.

The results of these surveys are presented in section 3.3, Science Communication. In the long term, we hope that studies measuring antibiotic consumption in Chile, such as the one conducted by Dr. Eili Klein published in 2018[3], will be periodically conducted again to know the effect of these education measures.

3) Finally, we expect our project to have an impact on public policies since, in addition to contributing to two of the five strategic lines of the National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance implemented by Chile, we conducted exhaustive research focused on Chile's integration into the Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS). The WHO launched this global collaborative effort to standardize AMR surveillance and what is currently happening with the antibiotic labeling law in Chile.

Regarding the incorporation of Chile into GLASS, based on the interviews conducted with the coordinator of the National Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance, Dr. Tania Herrera, and the Head of the Department of Infectious Diseases of the Public Health Institute, Dr. Juan Carlos Hormazábal, described in Section 2.3 Human Practices, we decided to contact the person directly responsible for this matter, which corresponds to the Minister of Health, Ximena Aguilera and the secretary of Health, Cristóbal Cuadrado, also described in section 2.3. Consequently, one way to assess the impact of this measure on the community is for our letter to the authorities to play a role in promoting Chile's incorporation into GLASS. On the other hand, concerning the antibiotic labeling law, we hope that the observations that we make to the parliamentarians in Congress will allow us to advance in the processing and correction of the law. One way to evaluate the impact of this measure is that it effectively incorporates a more rigorous regulation regarding the misuse of antibiotics and that, in the future, this can reduce the excessive consumption of antibiotics in Chile.

References:

- Byarugaba DK. A view on antimicrobial resistance in developing countries and responsible risk factors. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*. 2004;24:105–10

- Okeke IN, Klugman KP, Bhutta ZA, Duse AG, Jenkins P, O'Brien TF, et al. Antimicrobial resistance in developing countries. Part II: strategies for containment. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* 2005;5:568–80
- Klein, E. Y., Van Boeckel, T. P., Martinez, E. M., Pant, S., Gandra, S., Levin, S. A., ... & Laxminarayan, R. (2018). Global increase and geographic convergence in antibiotic consumption between 2000 and 2015. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(15), E3463-E3470.
- Marcoleta, A. E., Arros, P., Varas, M. A., Costa, J., Rojas-Salgado, J., Berríos-Pastén, C., & Lagos, R. (2022). The highly diverse Antarctic Peninsula soil microbiota as a source of novel resistance genes. *Science of The Total Environment*, 810, 15200

2.6 Impact on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

As a team and future synthetic biology leaders, we know the importance of the 2030 Agenda, and the role the accomplishment of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) plays in society. That's why we decided to build our project based on, what we considered, the three most important sustainable development goals or SDGs.

SDG 3 Good Health and Well-being: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global problem affecting different aspects of society but, specifically for humans, is a threat to Good Health and Well-being; SDG 3. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development highlights strengthening the capacity of all countries, particularly developing countries, for early warning, risk reduction, and management of national and global health risks (United Nations, 2015) as a critical step to accomplishing the third SDG.

Regarding contributing to SDGs, our project emphasizes three of them. First, as mentioned above, antibiotic resistance is a global threat to humanity, jeopardizing many of the 20th century's milestones. Therefore, we seek to fight antibiotic resistance around the world using our local biological systems to obtain inhibitory molecules against Antarctic resistance genes using synthetic biology so we can address this local problem that could worsen the actual resistance scene.

SDG 4 Quality Education: On the other hand, one of the main factors adding to the AMR crisis is the lack of information and myths about the use and abuse of antibiotics. Educating the population to prevent and eradicate the misuse of these drugs is key to stopping the advance of antibiotic resistance. By publishing free-access educational material, we aim to raise awareness among people of different ages, from children and adolescents to the adult population.

At the same time, we researched the state of the art of the Antibiotic Labeling Law, a project that seeks to give information to people about the use of antibiotics in different products. After the research, we realized that this law is not enough and that there

should be laws that regulate and restrict the use of antibiotics in the whole production chain. Furthermore, it is necessary to promote their disuse, we also shared a post about this (details 2.4 section), this last post was accompanied by other educational posts on antibiotic resistance in our social platforms, school workshops, and other activities (check these activities in sections: 2.4, 3.1, 3.3, and 3.6), to move on towards educating Chilean people on this topic. This is, once again an initiative aligned with SDG 4; Quality Education.

SDG 5 Gender Equality: Additionally, to address the gender gap problem in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) we established the fifth Sustainable Development Goal: Gender Equality, as our last essential pillar. To find new integrated solutions to antimicrobial resistance, we need different perspectives in science; hence, including women in this field is indispensable to finding answers to modern scientific interrogatives such as the Antarctic Peninsula soil-resistant bacteria. To enrich perspectives, we need to promote the participation of men and women equally. For this, we have ensured that all our actions and activities encourage equal participation of both sexes so women can be reflected as female scientific leaders and conquer new spaces. This is not an isolated initiative but a transversal plan to reach diversity in our team in every aspect throughout the competition (details in 3.5 Diversity and inclusion section).

To reach a much more diverse group of people, we teamed up with the CO2 Snatchers team, another 2022 iGEM Design League team from Mexico. The collaboration had as its central key point to promote SDGs by telling our audience about the sustainable development goals we were rooting for with our projects (see 3.1 Collaborations to read the full description).

To widen our perspective on SDGs and how the melting of permafrost, an event triggered by the Climate Crisis, can negatively impact the AMR crisis, two of our team members, Rocío González-Parada and Amelia Cox, participated in the Local

Conference of Youth (LCOY) 2022. The conference, supported by YOUNGO, offered different perspectives on the Climate Crisis and how the consequences will impact Latin American Communities, especially Chile. Furthermore, this experience allowed our team members to discuss the project with younger people concerned about climate change. Below is a picture of Amelia and Rocío in LCOY 2022.

On the left, Rocío González-Parada, and on the right, Amelia Cox.

Finally, to evaluate if our approach to SDGs was sustainable, we asked our primary stakeholders, such as the National Institute of Public Health, to judge our work and viewpoint in fighting AMR. To learn about the advice our stakeholders gave us, check our Project Video. Additionally, to measure our impact on SDGs we create surveys to collect relevant information of our audience and learn from the feedback, this is detailed and well explained in section 2.4 Integrated Human Practices .

2.7 Safety and Security

To accomplish the objectives proposed for our project (defined in section 2.2) our laboratories followed the Manual of Biosafety, established by the Superior Council of Science and Technological Development, from the National Fund of Scientific and Technological Development of Chile (FONDECYT). <https://www.conicyt.cl/fondecyt/2018/06/14/manual-de-normas-de-bioseguridad-2018/>.

We can also point out that our bacterial chassis for heterologous expression of the Antarctic genes will be a laboratory strain of *E. coli*, specifically DH5alpha, BL21, or similar, whose biosafety level is 2 according to the World Health Organization (WHO) Laboratory Biosafety Manual. Furthermore, our proposed bioparts have no evident activity that could be directly or indirectly used as a biological weapon or as a harmful or toxic substance and we will make sure that our protocols include low to no-risk materials and equipment. Thus, it is hard to anticipate any eventual malicious use of our bioparts and probably would involve unsuspected properties or deep modifications of our bricks and chassis.

3.1 Collaborations

Resistance team: Fenix

Fénix was one of our favorite collaborations! Why? Because we choose the same topic: Antibiotic Resistance. With Fénix, we wanted to 1) spread to the people the problem of Antibiotic Resistance and our synthetic biology-based solutions 2) and contribute to education on synthetic biology. So, in order to achieve both of them, we decided to make a *live* on Instagram from our project accounts to talk about 1) the problem of Antibiotic Resistance globally and then in our contexts, 2) our synthetic biology-based solutions, 3) and the experience of both groups through the time of competition. To promote the *live*, we did a poster together using a standard editing file in Canva and then published it on both Instagram project accounts. We had some online meetings to plan the *live* and create the poster.

However, that was just one of the things that we did together. Also, Team Fénix did a class about genetic engineering in our Tan-Tári Open Academy -more details about Tan-Tári Open Academy in the 3.3 Science Communication section in order to contribute to the democratization of knowledge and teach about widely used techniques in synthetic biology, in line with our second objective of the collaboration. This class was done through the Zoom platform, and then we uploaded it to our YouTube channel so anyone could watch it. We want to mention that we asked Fénix for a woman to do the class because, as a team, we proposed that 50% of our teachers at Tan-Tari Open Academy should be women, in line with one of the SDGs that we chose: 5, and Fénix accepted it. So together, we helped each team to reach the 4 and 5 SDGs. To promote this class, we made a poster with information about the class and published it on our Instagram account. Below is the link of the open class done by Fénix:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D-VMLiqibug&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

In line with the educational objective, Fénix asked us if we could do a class about the antibiotic resistance problem we decided to tackle and our synthetic biology-based

solution in their University Biotechnological Week on the 4th of November, so we enthusiastically accepted! Was such a great activity!

Below are all the posts to promote the live and Fénix class in Tan-Tári Open Academy and the live stats. It is essential to mention that, because of our technical problems, we uploaded a second version of the session where we cut them.

We want to mention that we had several online meetings to reach our goals and plan the activities. In these meetings, we also talked about our projects and asked each

other questions about the competition's deliverables and other stuff. Also, we did a Whatsapp group called "Resistance Team" to define the meeting days and some details about the activities. Finally, during competition time, we also used this group to ask about doubts that appeared.

IBERO puebla:

Ibero Puebla was an extraordinary team to collaborate with; we had a very positive attitude and great energy in all the meetings. We proposed to reach two objectives 1) spread the problem and solution that both teams were working with to raise people's awareness and 2) help each other teams to get more followers on Instagram to reach a wider audience with the project content.

In order to achieve the first objective, we discussed some ideas. Finally, we decided to do a collaborative poster about bacteria so that both teams could address their topics. We collaboratively did this poster by creating a structure in an online meeting and then editing the poster together in a shared file on Canva and checking the final version in an online meeting. We published it on both Instagram Team accounts.

To reach the second objective, we did a giveaway on our Instagram accounts, where the prize was a bacteria plushie to bring microorganisms closer to people in a friendly way. We created the poster by editing a shared Canva file and checked the final version in an online meeting. Finally, we did an Instagram Live to carry out the draw for the plushie, and then we designed a poster to announce the winner.

We want to mention that we had several meetings in which we talked about the objectives of the collaboration, did a brainstorm to reach them, and also helped each other with doubts about the competition. Moreover, our Team Leader shared her experience in the iGEM competition to give them advice and tips that could help iGEM Ibero Puebla because it was their first experience in the iGEM world. Furthermore, we created a Whatsapp group to coordinate some things and answer questions about the deliverables during the competition.

Below is the first post we did together, the giveaway post, the result of the giveaway post, and their stats.

Raising public awareness of sustainable development objectives with the CO2 Snatchers team

We collaborated with CO2 snatchers focused on the SDGs. The two main objectives were 1) to promote SDGs among people and 2) to show that scientific projects can be built around them. In order to achieve these objectives, we had some online meetings where we discussed what and how we could achieve our objectives. Finally, we publish a video on our Instagram account (reel format). Making this video was a creative, collaborative, and fun process: we had a meeting to brainstorm ideas for the video and its script. The last meeting was centered on video editing with a shared Canva mp4 file.

Through this process, we had several online meetings where both teams exposed their ideas, and we voted to choose the best one. In the last meeting, we took a picture with posters of the SDGs of both groups. We published the video on both accounts and got 1705 views -to date.

The link to our reel:

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/CiTNr2TMUzN/?igshid=NDc0ODY0MjQ=>

We created a Whatsapp group called The Power of Chile in honor of the common element between México and Chile. We want to highlight that we discussed our projects and feelings regarding handling the competition during the meetings. We kept in touch through the Whatsapp group, and we used it to ask some questions that arose about the competition.

iGEMERS History and spreading science with iGEM Biotech EC

iGEM Biotech EC invited us to be part of their “**iGEMERS History**” project. This idea was about documenting the process and experiences of the different teams through the competition, and we thought that was a great idea! So, we sent some pictures and wrote a summary of our experience. It was a beautiful exercise to select the moments and the words. Below are some of the pictures we chose and the text we wrote (the original one is in Spanish, but we translated it for this JOGL section).

“...In the beginning, we faced doubts and insecurities. However, the team is characterized by having an enormous disposition, good work dynamics, and a remarkable ability to help, which was crucial for overcoming the obstacles that have come our way. Our work has been done organically, and although we adjust our times and lives, we have always given the best of ourselves. In a short time, we have managed to build a beautiful project with a scientific, educational, and gender approach, axes that move us as people. In addition, we have connected with different teams from

different parts of Latin America, which has allowed us to broaden our views and learn from collaborative work between teams”.

We also joined another collaboration with iGEM Biotech EC: Scientific Monologues. They invited us to create a video with a scientific monologue in which we presented the project in an understandable way to a broad audience. We decided to make a video for children because they are always forgotten when discussing serious problems. However, they are the future generation that will have to deal with them, so we thought that solutions could be developed through synthetic biology if they had a better understanding of the antibiotic crisis. This action could diminish the crisis and plant a vocational, scientific seed in them. We used this opportunity to be more inclusive with one of our mentors living in Cuba during most of the competition time, so being present during in-person meetings was impossible for her. Also, sometimes she needed help with her connection. With her little daughter's feedback, she helped us create the video

script, and we animated it with pictures of Ian and her daughter. It was a very special way to connect with Ian (details about this inclusion action in the 3.5 Diversity and inclusion section). Below we left the link to the video:

<https://www.instagram.com/tv/CkJiJx1AHJf/?igshid=NDc0ODY0MjQ=>

Building a collective photographic memory in LATAM to raise awareness of pollution with iGEM FCB-UANL y iGEM BIOTECH EC

iGEM FCB-UANL invited us to collaborate in their photographic contest, "Impact of climate change on communities in Latin America" we thought it was a creative and artistic way to raise pollution awareness, so we joined. Also, iGEM Biotech EC joined this activity.

The purpose of this contest was to artistically represent through photography the negative repercussions of climate change on Latin American communities, leading to a reflection and awareness described.

The photographs were oriented to capture the adverse effects of climate change on flora and fauna of the city/town. This activity was developed under the principles of the 11, 13, and 15 SDGs. In addition, considering that this was a way to educate people about pollution and responsible civilian behavior, we considered that this activity also reached the 3 and 4 SDGs. Considering our results, we could have developed and shared other SDGs like 9, 10, 12, 14, and 17.

Below is the link to the post with the corresponding contest call and also the post with the photographs.

IGEM FCB-UANL - TAN TÁRI BRICKS - iGEM BIOTECH EC

convocan

CONCURSO DE FOTOGRAFÍA

"Repercusión del cambio climático en las comunidades de Latino América"

¡EXTENSIÓN DE 1 SEMANA MÁS!
Premios tarjetas de regalo Amazon

amazon

Primer lugar:
25 dólares

Segundo lugar:
15 dólares

IGEM FCB-UANL - TAN TÁRI BRICKS - iGEM BIOTECH EC

Representa mediante la fotografía las repercusiones del cambio climático en la flora y fauna de tu ciudad/pueblo.

Orientado para todo el público

Vigencia 22 de agosto al 10 de septiembre

Especificaciones:

1. Prohibido utilizar material de terceros como propio.
2. Subir 1 fotografía formato PNG o JPG por participante y llenar el formulario en el QR.
3. Evitar uso de filtros, sólo se permite corrección de contraste y luz.
4. Al finalizar la convocatoria, las mejores 10 fotografías seleccionadas serán publicadas en Facebook: /uanligem.
5. En un plazo de 1 semana, las dos fotografías con más likes y shares públicos estarán sujetas a los premios*

Más información:
Formulario

*ver las especificaciones detalladas en el formulario

Instagram post with the photos:

<https://www.instagram.com/p/CjT0LmkO0gu/?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y=>

Mentorships with OllinSynbio

In the soft skills session, we participated by answering the question that the corresponding professor asked. We learned important things about positive leadership, how to work in a team, and deal with some tricky situations that could occur in an intense competition such as iGEM DL.

We want to highlight that for the first mentorship, a Whatsapp group was created with all the iDL teams that assisted, and we used it during the whole period of the competition to share our activities and solve some questions. It was constructive!

Iktan kan ek: Let's talk about our projects!

We had an online meeting with *Iktan tan ek* to discuss our projects. It was an excellent session where we had the opportunity to discuss the problems we were trying to solve,

the possible problems associated with the solutions that each team was developing, and our own experiences during the competition.

In this online meeting, Amelia and one of our mentors: Patricio, participated. *Ikan tan ek* asked us some questions about our strategy, and this led us to the possibility of improving the way we communicated our project. Furthermore, we discussed how our projects could have a potential economic impact on our countries. This discussion was a positive opportunity for us to gather some ideas on the economic aspects of our project, which we had yet to consider before, such as boosting the local pharmaceutical industry by promoting the synthesis of new antimicrobials in our country.

Something remarkable was that *Iktan tan ek* faced the eutrophication issue, a problem associated with Red Tide. That was the topic that iGEM Team UChile Biotec 2017, in which Amelia participated, aimed for with the Bimatox project. Consequently, this led to a rich discussion, and Amelia gave some important advice and observations about Iktan tan ek's project. Interestingly, even the mascot they had chosen -a snake- was the same one that Team UChile Biotec 2018 chose when they continued the Bimatox project from the previous year.

Breaking the geographical barrier: let's help spread iGEM DL projects!

In order to achieve the following two objectives: 1) to help other iGEM DL teams to get known 2) and to spread Latin American synthetic biology projects, we wrote through Instagram to all the teams that we could reach their accounts. We asked them to send us a poster with the members of the team and their Instagram project account to be exposed in a video loop at the Symposium we organized (more information about the Symposium in the 3.3 Science communication section). Also, we made a video with all the posters sent and shared it on our Instagram account, having 926 views. Thus, we could help iGEM DL teams reach more followers on Instagram and reach our two main objectives.

The following teams sent us the poster with the aforementioned characteristics: 1. Fénix, 2. Ollin Synbio, 3. iGEM TEC QRO, 4. IKAN KAN EK, 5. IGEM UNMSM, 6. iGEM Biotech EC, 7. iGEM Ibero Puebla, 8. FCB-UANL. In the link below, the video that we posted on our Instagram can be found:

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/CiAuYnIguYB/?igshid=NDc0ODY0MjQ=>

Below, you will find some of the pictures of the several online meetings that we had with the different iDL teams which we collaborate with (Fenix, IberoPuebla, CO2 Snatchers, Ollin Synbio and Iktan Kan ek).

Pitch and Match: We want to mention that we participated in the event organized by the iGEM Community, "Pitch and Match," an activity aimed at fostering collaboration between iGEM Competition and iGEM DL teams. We did not initiate any collaboration in this instance, but it was an excellent opportunity to learn about other projects and practice the scientific communication of our project.

3.2 Entrepreneurship

N/A

3.3 Science communication

3.3.1 Social media and educational content: For the first part of the competition, we were focused on creating content for Instagram to bring information to all kinds of people without barriers of knowledge, age, gender, or nationality. Thus, for a wider reach, all the information was shared in Spanish and English. In addition, a Youtube channel and a mirror Twitter account were created.

For the first part of the competition, we were focused on creating content for Instagram, to bring information to all kinds of people, without barriers of knowledge, age, gender or nationality. Thus, for a wider reach, all the information was shared in two languages, Spanish and English.

We shared information about our team and essential concepts that helped us explain the project while promoting science and synthetic biology. We also shared relevant information about the iGEM Design League competition and the pros and cons of the problem we are addressing as a team. Also, we left links of interest in our link in bio on our Instagram account. All this was possible after consolidating a graphic line and a color palette that helped us maintain an aesthetic that allowed coherence in all the material uploaded. Also, the content created had to be accompanied by a character that could connect with the Instagram public. Therefore, designing a mascot for the team -Tarito- created an attractive and accessible profile to deliver our information.

@TANTARIBRICKS INSTAGRAM ACCOUNT

To reach a broader audience, we contacted diverse groups dedicated to scientific communities (CienciaF5, the National Association of Biotechnology Engineering Students (ANEIB), the National Association of Biochemistry Students (ANEB), and the Association of Biology Students of Chile (AEBCH). These associations helped us share our events, activities, and educational posts on their Instagram and web pages. However, as more than promotion was needed to engage with new audiences, we also created a collaborative post with CienciaF5 and iDL teams like CO2 Snatchers and Ibero Puebla (check section 3.1. for further information on collaborations).

The note on the promotion of our Tan-Tári Open Academy by the ANEIB website and the collaborative post with CienciaF5 can be found in the following links.

ANEIB Note:

<https://aneib.cl/post/invitacion-tan-tari-open-academy--biologia-sintetica-disenando-la-vida/>

Collaboration post with CienciaF5:

<https://www.instagram.com/p/Ci0vOEquVfA/>

With this approach, we created a communication platform reaching 4,500 people in October and growing since the creation of the page at the beginning of the competition with 61 posts. In addition, this approach met our team's ideals by reaching different countries, age ranges, and even equal gender demographics.

These stats demonstrate that using social media to share truthful information with credited sources is essential to combat fake news. All of this concurs with the Quality Education SDG selected by our team.

Lastly, we are preparing an E-Book that compiles all of the educational material created by our team through these months, so it can be shared on other platforms and seen by as many people as possible.

3.3.2 Activities to share and educate about antibiotic resistance, synthetic Biology and iGEM DL.

3.3.2.1 Tan-Tári Open Academy: Throughout the competition, and after talking to our university classmates, we discovered that most people did not know the meaning of synthetic biology. Thus, we decided to create the *Tan-Tári Open Academy*, a series of three open access synthetic biology classes, starting from the basic. In our quest to find an exceptional candidate to teach about this relatively new topic, we bumped into Carlos Vidal, a molecular biotechnology engineer devoted to synthetic biology. He created two introductory classes for students, with topics such as biological cassettes, biobricks, and biological gates.

In these classes, we reached 50 students either in-person or through the online stream. Regarding *Tan-Tári Open Academy*, the open class collaboration with the iDL team should be mentioned: Fénix (detailed in section 3.1.), where we shared knowledge about antibiotic resistance, and they taught about genetic engineering techniques. Below are the links to our three sessions.

Carlos Vidal Session 1 out of 2:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7r8WuzoWlqg&t=393s&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

Carlos Vidal Session 2 out of 2:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=arPFtIsGt00&t=2s&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

Fénix class:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D-VMLiqibug&t=91s&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

To know how much people who enrolled in our Tan-Tári Open Academy sessions knew about synthetic biology, antibiotic resistance, and iGEM, we surveyed them. Seeing that many people did not know iGEM or synthetic biology before our classes were essential to planning and improving the Tan-Tári Academy sessions. That proved that these sessions were necessary to spread these topics to the community. Below can be found the results of the survey:

CLASSES ON ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE SURVEY RESULTS

WHAT DO YOU KNOW?

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IS THE ABILITY OF A MICROORGANISM TO SURVIVE THE ACTION OF AN ANTIBIOTIC AGENT THROUGH GENETIC ELEMENTS, WHICH CAN BE SPONTANEOUS MUTATIONS OR THE IMPORTATION OF MOBILE GENETIC MATERIAL. CURRENTLY THIS PHENOMENON IS ONE OF THE MAIN HEALTH PROBLEMS WORLDWIDE

IT IS THE NEXT MOST SERIOUS GLOBAL PUBLIC HEALTH PROBLEM DUE TO SUPER RESISTANT BACTERIA

RESISTANCE TO ANTIBIOTICS HAPPENS THROUGH NATURAL SELECTION. CERTAIN BACTERIA MUTATE, GENERATING RESISTANCE TO THE ANTIBIOTIC THAT KILLED THEM, AND THEY REPRODUCE, GENERATING A PROBLEM OF A POSSIBLE DEPLETION OF ANTIBIOTICS TO BE USED

IT IS THE ABILITY THAT GENERATES CERTAIN BACTERIA TO THIS AFTER EVOLVING IN ORDER TO LIVE

IT IS THE MECHANISM BY WHICH MICROORGANISMS SUCH AS BACTERIA DEVELOP AN IMPEDIMENT SO THAT ANTIBIOTICS DO NOT TAKE EFFECT.

HAVE YOU HEARD ABOUT OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE?

DO YOU THINK IT IS IMPORTANT THAT THERE ARE PROJECTS LIKE OURS THAT SEEK TO DEVELOP NEW STRATEGIES TO COMBAT BACTERIA?

TAN-TÁRI OPEN ACADEMY SURVEY RESULTS

HAVE YOU HEARD OF SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY BEFORE?

HAVE YOU HEARD ABOUT THE IGEM COMPETITION BEFORE THIS ACTIVITY?

HOW DID YOU FIND OUT ABOUT THE ACTIVITY?

CLASSES ON ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE SURVEY RESULTS

HAVE YOU HEARD ABOUT ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE?

DO YOU THINK THAT SCIENCE IS IMPORTANT TO FIND SOLUTIONS TO THE GREAT PROBLEMS THAT AFFECT HUMANITY?

DID YOU KNOW THAT YOU CAN HELP REDUCE THE RATE AT WHICH IT IS GENERATED BY PERFORMING CERTAIN BEHAVIORS?

TAN-TÁRI OPEN ACADEMY SURVEY RESULTS

AGES OF ENROLLEES

GENDER OF ATTENDEES

PARTICIPATION MODE

3.3.2.2 Symposium: “iGEM: World’s biggest synthetic biology student competition”: Considering that few people know about iGEM Design League or the iGEM competition, we were determined to share our project with national biotech startups and to many people as possible. We organized the symposium, **“iGEM: World's biggest synthetic biology student competition,”** where another 50 students enrolled. We counted the following speakers:

- Natalie Edwards: who participated in the iGEM Competition in 2018 with Team UChile_Biotec from our Faculty (Faculty of Science, University of Chile).
- Alejandra Oyarzo: who participated in the iGEM Competition in 2017 with Team UChile_Biotec and is also part of the iDL Staff.
- Samantha García Arias, who is an iGEM Latam Ambassador.
- Two representatives of national startups -Protera and Pewman- participated as speakers: Enzo Galliani, Project Development Manager at Pewman, also participated in iGEM Competition as part of the Team UChile_Biotec 2017 and Dr. Leonardo Álvarez Protera's CEO.

They spoke about biotechnology entrepreneurship in Chile and shared some of this year's competitors' posters to showcase the variety of work being made in the competition (this collaboration is detailed in section 3.1.). Furthermore, we also presented our team, our project considering the problem of antibiotic resistance, our synthetic biology-based solution, our SDGs, and our lines of action. It is important to note that we did this symposium aiming that 50% of the speakers must be women -SDG 5- and we are so proud that we reached it.

This Symposium was only possible with the collaboration with the iGEM Design League staff. We had several online meetings and kept in touch by email to improve our initial proposal. Initially, this activity would be just online and without national biotech startups. Thanks to iDL staff advice, we did a hybrid instance with online and in-person participants. We incorporated two national biotech startups - one of them a former iGEM

participant- and also contacted Samantha Garcia and Leonardo from Protera and Alejandra Oyarzo, designer at iGEM DL. Below can be found a picture of one of our online meetings:

To appeal to younger students, with the help of our instructors, we reached out to high schoolers who participated in the workshops (see sections 2.4 and 3.6). We introduced them to the basic concepts of synthetic biology and, more importantly, invited them to participate in iGEM Design League, as we know they are one of the audiences for which this ramification of iGEM was designed. We hope they can take this opportunity to learn and discover the great possibilities unlocked with synthetic biology.

To fully comprehend the topics in the Symposium, **we developed a previous educational material** -SDG 4- that we sent before the Symposium to all the people who enrolled up to this event. In this material, we made a list of key concepts and left links to Spanish YouTube videos to provide an attractive explanation for each concept. Furthermore, we provided links of interest related to iGEM and iGEM DL web pages, wikis of previous teams from our University, and the United Nations page of SDGs.

Below is the link to this previous educational material and the YouTube link where our Symposium can be watched.

Link symposium:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PmY4xv4Fo-g&t=5529s&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

Link educative previous material:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rvPFOx0kXRZ2WK2kRlUtjhR5i09SoghV/view?usp=sharing>

Finally, we did a previous survey to determine how much people who enrolled knew about iGEM, antibiotic resistance, and synthetic biology. With this information, we could tell our speakers which topics were necessary to afford, and also we considered them when designing our presentation. Below can be found the results of the survey:

3.3.2.3 School students workshops: Considering that one of our lines of action is educating people to raise awareness about the antibiotic crisis, we did two workshops for school students, as they are the future generations who will fight against this problem. However, we also used this opportunity to spread our project, its synthetic biology-based solution, and the impact of iGEM. Consequently, as part of these activities, we talked about these topics. As seen in the 3.6 section, students made iGEM's logo with microorganisms in one of these workshops. We surveyed both workshops; more details can be found in the 3.6 and 2.4 sections.

3.3.2.4 Educational capsules: all the interviews that we did with our stakeholders were transformed into educational capsules published on our YouTube channel (details in section 2.4)

3.3.3 Publishing notes and communicational alliances

3.3.3.1 University of Chile portal: To attract visibility to the competition and our project, we contacted one journalist from our University, who wrote a note on our University's webpage with quotes about our experience during the competition and the team goals.

Link University of Chile webpage

<https://uchile.cl/noticias/191749/estudiantes-compiten-en-torneo-internacional-de-biologia-sintetica>

3.3.3.2 Ciencia en Chile: Finally, we got in touch with Ciencia en Chile -Science in Chile in english- a national press media specialized in scientific topics, and published a note about our project. Below is the link:

<https://www.cienciaenchile.cl/estudiantes-compiten-en-torneo-internacional-de-biologia-sintetica-con-modelo-para-evaluar-riesgos-de-bacterias-antarticas/>

3.3.3.3 Faculty of Science portal, University of Chile: To reach more people and spread synthetic biology-based solutions, we wrote to the Communication department of our Faculty to publish a note about our project presentation video and participation in IDL.

PUBLISHING NOTES AND COMMUNICATIONAL ALLIANCES

3.3.3.4 Communicational alliances: mBioClim and Instituto Milenio BASE: To continue our communication strategy, we allied with mBioClim (<http://mBioClim.cl>), a Project from the Chilean government called "*Antarctic microbiology of climate change: unearthing unknown virulence and resistance genes*". mBioClim is financed by the National Agency of Investigation and Development (ANID) and sponsored by the Antarctic Chilean Institute (INACH). They shared an invitation to our iGEM Symposium through their web page and we shared some posts about their project on our Instagram. Below is the link to the mBioClim webpage displaying the invitation to our Symposium.

<https://mbioclim.cl/tan-tari-bricks-junto-a-mbioclim-invitan-a-participar-del-simposio-igem-la-competencia-estudiantil-de-biologia-sintetica-mas-grande-del-mundo/>

Furthermore, we got in touch with Instituto Milenio BASE (Biodiversity Antarctic and Sub-Antarctic Ecosystems), because they afford topics related to Antarctica and its ecosystem, to spread our project, social networks and iGEM Design League Competition.

Link with the publication of our project in Instituto Milenio BASE twitter:

<https://mobile.twitter.com/MilenioBASE/status/1587873641630519299>

3.4 Public policy and regulation

N/A

3.5 Diversity and inclusion

Gender equality in our team: Besides choosing “SDG 4: Gender Equality” as one of our main pillars, our first challenge even before signing up for the competition, was to build a team with the same amount of women and men, a goal we are delighted to reach by consolidating a team of 15 people, 7 women and 8 men, led by a woman; Amelia Cox. Likewise, we two out of three commissions were led by women, in this case, Amelia Cox coordinated the General Coordination, Human Practices and Collaborations Commission, and Rocío González the Content, Design and Communications Commission.

Gender equality in our activities: We established that all of our activities must meet gender equality since we chose SDG 5 as one of our SDGs. Throughout the competition, the General Coordination, Human Practices and Collaborations

Commission was entrusted to organize the Tan-Tári Open Academy (synthetic biology open classes), but as we prepared for the event, we encountered an alarming problem: most of the Chilean scientists specializing in synthetic biology were men. This is a serious problem since we are giving a wrong impression to the younger generations, we are convinced that more female and non-binary synthetic biology scientists are needed so children have them as role models. To improve diversity is necessary to implement programs that promote the participation of women and non-binary people to establish gender equality in synthetic biology.

In order to reach this, for example, we asked Fénix to impart a class on our Tan-Tári Open Academy with the condition that the class was taught by a woman. The request was accepted (details in section 3.2), allowing our team to once again reach gender equality since 50% of the Tan-Tári Open Academy professors were women. Furthermore, in the symposium that we organized, we set ourselves a goal that 50% of the speakers must be women, and we achieved it (details in section 3.3).

Maternal care and science: One of the biggest challenges to maintaining the female presence throughout the scientific career is facilitating the compatibility of scientific work with maternal care, both extremely demanding. This is why one of the activities we carried out had the implicit objective of exemplifying that this challenge is possible to face: Ian, one of the team's mentors, and her little daughter were the protagonists in one of our videos, a special way to demonstrate that with enthusiasm and creativity barriers can be overcome for women and girls in science (see the 3.1 section to know the activity in question).

Multicultural and interdisciplinary team: Along with gender equality, our team was also concerned with forming a multicultural team. Consequently, we recruited a team representing Chile composed of people coming from Chile, Argentina, Cuba, Spain, and Venezuela, dedicated to different academic fields, such as molecular biotechnology engineering, environmental sciences, microbiology, and architecture and urban

planning. By means of these actions, we sought to reinforce the conformation of not only a multidisciplinary but also an inclusive and diverse team in the iGEM Design League competition and in science.

Besides the gender issue, it is important to highlight the need to take synthetic biology beyond the scientific field, expanding it to different disciplines of higher education and to local communities. It is crucial the communication of synthetic biology to local communities to expand this field out of start-ups and businesses, putting synthetic biology at disposal of local needs, especially in the conservation and preservation of ecosystems.

Breaking knowledge & language barriers: It is worth mentioning that most of our educational posts published on our Instagram account were both in English and Spanish, to reach a broader audience; in addition, we published on our YouTube channel: all the Tan-Tári Open Academy sessions, our symposium and the interviews of the stakeholders in order to democratize knowledge (details section 3.3). Furthermore, as you can see in sections 1.3 and 1.4, we included Spanish subtitles in both the promotional video and project presentation video, considering deaf people of our native language; besides, we included Portuguese subtitles in our promotional video thinking about our Brazilian friends.

Safe work environment: On the other hand, to create a safe and fair environment, from the beginning we established a series of rules to ensure healthy relationships among team members, based on respect and tolerance. We established a safe environment of work, a place where every idea was welcomed and none of them were more valuable than the others. In other words, every intervention made by the people on our team was carefully and respectfully listened to without any judgment.

In addition to this, we created instances in our weekly meetings that allowed us to communicate how we were feeling throughout the competition, especially when a

deadline was approaching. This way, we always made sure our team members were feeling motivated and having a good time while working on our project. These moments enabled us to grow as a team and verbalize our complaints, improving our working methods and the way we communicate our feelings and needs. We also took advantage of those moments to get to know each other better, sharing multiple laughs and enjoying our time working together.

3.6 Arts and creativity

We believe that art is a valuable tool to learn biology, spread knowledge and even make ourselves and our project known. For this reason, we carried out different actions that involved art which are described below. Thus, in this section, you will find the intersections with art that we had! Was a very funny part of our project and a good way to develop our creativity.

- **Poster Kick off**

One of our first intersections with art was the design of the official team members' poster, which was sent and displayed at the kick-off ceremony to make the team known. For the designing process, we did a brainstorm in an online meeting and defined representative elements and colors of our project.

- **Development of a graphic line**

Our second encounter with art was the development of our brand, which contemplated the definition of a color pallet, fonts, and a mascot. One of the first meetings was a brainstorming session to define our team's colors, logo, and mascot, the best ones were

Tān-Tāri Bricks

Amelia Cox

Molecular Biotechnology
Engineering
Team Leader

Rocio González

Molecular Biotechnology
Engineering
Student member

José Coche

Molecular Biotechnology
Engineering
Student member

Gabriela Carrasco

Molecular Biotechnology
Engineering
Student member

Hugo González

Environmental Biology
Student member

Macarena Gajardo

Architecture and Urban planning
Student member

Francisco Chávez

PhD in Microbiology
Main advisor

Andrés Marcoleta

PhD in Microbiology
Instructor

Julieta Orlando

PhD in Microbiology
Instructor

Patricio Arros

PhD student in
Microbiology Sciences
Mentor

Ian Perez

PPhD student in Microbiology
Sciences
Mentor

Antonia Ramos

MSc student in Biological Sciences
Mentor

Claudio Valenzuela

PhD student in Molecular
Biotechnology
Mentor

Camilo Berríos

PhD student in Microbiology
Mentor

Jorge Vielma Salazar

MSc student in Biological
Sciences
Mentor

taken by the Content, Design and Communications Commission who researched different elements like the south of Chile, the Yagán culture, Magallanes -the southernmost region of Chile (fun fact: our actual president was born there!)- Chilean icebergs, synthetic biology, and antibiotics. The result of this process was a proposal voted by the whole team, which included voting for their favorite fonts, logo, and colors. Below you can find the proposal made by the Content, Design and Communications Commission.

GRAPHIC LINE AND COLOR PALETTE

CS GORDON RPUNDED

CS GORDON RPUNDED

Betm rounded

Betm rounded

Betm rounded

TEAM'S MASCOT: TARITO

- **Art workshop with microorganisms and art exhibit**

To promote synthetic biology, raise awareness on iGEM DL, and educate school children on the antibiotic resistance problem, we conducted an art workshop with microorganisms. In this instance, students used agar, microorganisms, antibiotics,

paintbrushes and eva rubber molds to make works of art. This activity entailed an implicit challenge: avoiding children's phobia to microorganisms while explaining to them the huge diversity of these living creatures, some of them beneficial and others pathogenic, both for humans and for other animals.

One of the results of this workshop was the word iGEM formed by school students on several plates. The result was transferred to paper by printing the plates with the bacterial growth obtained.

Click the link below to watch the video with some moments of this school workshop in our university laboratories:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPkEpSU1IWQ&ab_channel=TanTariBricks

At the end of the activity, we conducted a survey to find out what the students learned and their impressions of the activity. Below you can find the questions and the answers of the survey (the original was in Spanish), but were translated the answers for the JOGL.

ART WITH MICROORGANISMS WORKSHOP SURVEY RESULTS

DID YOU KNOW ANYTHING ABOUT MICROORGANISMS AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE BEFORE THIS ACTIVITY?

IF YOU ANSWERED "YES" TO THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, COULD YOU BRIEFLY TELL US WHAT YOU KNEW?

I KNEW THAT SUPER RESISTANT MICROORGANISMS ARE BEING GENERATED.

I KNEW HOW RESISTANT BACTERIA REPRODUCE IN ORDER TO GENERATE TOTAL RESISTANCE TO AN INTRODUCED ANTIBIOTIC.

THAT THEY COULD BECOME RESISTANT

I'M NOT REALLY SURE BECAUSE MY NATURE IS VERY CURIOUS AND I KEEP LOOKING UP HOW ADHESIVE TAPE IS MADE, SO I HAVE SO MUCH INTERESTING INFORMATION ENTERING MY BRAIN THAT I'M NOT SURE.

I KNEW THAT ANTIBIOTICS ARE COMPOUNDS THAT KILL OR PREVENT THE GROWTH OF PATHOGENIC AND NON-PATHOGENIC BACTERIA, AND THAT THEIR CONSTANT USE, THEIR INDISCRIMINATE USE, CAUSES THE RESISTANCE OF BACTERIA TO THEM, AND COULD ALSO CAUSE DISEASES SINCE SOME ANTIBIOTICS NOT ONLY KILL PATHOGENIC BACTERIA, BUT BENEFICIAL BACTERIA AS WELL, ALSO, SINCE BACTERIA MAKE GENETIC TRANSFER AMONG THEMSELVES, THEY ACQUIRE THE GENETIC INFORMATION OF OTHER BACTERIA TO NEUTRALIZE THE EFFECTS OF ANTIBIOTICS AND THUS BECOME MULTI RESISTANT.

COULD YOU TELL US WHAT NEW LESSONS YOU LEARNED FROM THIS ACTIVITY AND/OR WHAT STOOD OUT THE MOST FOR YOU?

I LEARNED HOW BACTERIAL CULTURE WORKS AND HOW IMAGES CAN BE GENERATED FROM IT.

INFORMATION ON BACTERIAL COLONIES, HOW THEY ARE GROUPED AND HOW TO STAIN THEM SO THAT THEY ARE VISIBLE TO THE HUMAN EYE.

THE ABILITY TO MODIFY THE ORDER OF THE COLONIES IN ORDER TO WRITE OR PAINT

COLONIES CAN BE MOVED AND SHAPES CAN BE FORMED

THE ACTIVITY SATISFIED MY CURIOSITY AND EXCEEDED MY EXPECTATIONS, I HAD A GREAT TIME.

WHAT I LEARNED FROM THIS ACTIVITY WAS THAT BACTERIA CAN BE CLASSIFIED INTO TWO DIFFERENT GROUPS, GRAM POSITIVE AND GRAM NEGATIVE BACTERIA, GRAM NEGATIVE BACTERIA HAVE A DOUBLE MEMBRANE AND WHEN STAINED THEIR COLOR IS RED OR PINK, AND GRAM POSITIVE BACTERIA HAVE ONLY ONE MEMBRANE AND WHEN STAINED THE COLOR THEY ACQUIRE IS BLUE. I ALSO LEARNED THAT BACTERIA LIVE AND ORGANIZE THEMSELVES IN COLONIES, WHAT CAUGHT MY ATTENTION WAS THE MICROSCOPIC SIZE OF THESE, SINCE IN SUCH A SMALL SPACE AS THE PETRI DISHES WERE, THERE COULD BE MILLIONS OF BACTERIA LIVING TOGETHER. IN ADDITION, THE STRONG EFFECT THAT ANTIBIOTICS HAVE ON BACTERIA, SINCE WITH A LITTLE ANTIBIOTIC, BACTERIA WERE UNABLE TO REPRODUCE.

INTERESTED IN LEARNING MORE ABOUT SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY AND THE iGEM INTERNATIONAL COMPETITION?

Thanks to this survey, we noted that the knowledge about antibiotic resistance before this activity was a basic one, so we contribute to deepening it. Also, we showed them how bacteria can be used to make art and that was something that students enjoyed a lot. Furthermore, we could spread synthetic biology and the iGEM world and generate interest in them.

The prints were exhibited in a small art exhibition that we made after one of the Tan Tári Open Academy sessions, where we also exhibited a video of the workshop and our mascot, Tarito, crocheted by our member Gabriela Carrasco, to bring the project closer to the people. Using this wool-made Tarito, we told the story of the project and why we chose him as our mascot. In this same exhibition, copies of the book **"De cobre, microbios y arte"** ("Of copper, microbes and art") were exhibited, the piece was co-authored by our Team Instructor Dr. Andrés Marcoleta and the prologue was written by Dr. Julieta Orlando, also Team Instructor. Thus, those who were interested in learning more about art with microorganisms would have a source from where to start, since it deals with art techniques using different types of microorganisms and the relevant protocols are cited, you can also find reflections about the role of art in science and vice versa. In addition to this, four books were raffled among those who attended the first two sessions of Tan Tári Open Academy,. It is worth mentioning that the link for the free and legal download of the book was sent by mail to the attendees and we also left it in the video about the art workshop with microorganisms that we published on our Instagram and YouTube channel.

Click de link below to download the book *"Of copper, microbes and art"*

<https://repositorio.uchile.cl/handle/2250/184464>

- **Tan Tári Bricks logo: with antibiotics and bacteria!!**

We wanted to do our logo with antibiotics and bacteria, in order to mix these two core elements of our problem in a creative way that could be attractive to people. So, we talked with André Barbet, an specialist of art with microorganisms and one of the authors of the book *"Of copper, microbes and art"*, and he helped us with the realization of this work.

In the banner below you can see the result of the workshop with school students and the logo made with André Barbet:

- **Comic strip starring Tarito**

In order to bring our project closer to people in a more friendly and fun way, we created a comic strip with Tarito as the main character. In this piece, we narrate the origin of our mascot, the name of the team and its context, and the problem we are addressing. We uploaded the comic to our networks and it is part of the E-Book we are currently working on.

TARITO "EL HIELITO"

The comic and the context of it in the following document:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jXD_FKDLonpeX46-CDw4rO2hZmehGVv/view?usp=sharing

- **Boxing charts**

We wanted to be able to tell our friends and family about the problem we addressed with our project and our solution based on synthetic biology, and we wanted to promote design with biology too. So, it occurred to us that a simple way to explain it could be illustrations where the problem versus the solution was graphed, through a vintage style in the frame of a boxing match, like boxer's cards! This is why our instructor, Dr. Chavez contacted us with a well-known illustrator, Alen Lauzan, to whom we explained our idea and through a process of continuous feedback we were able to reach the final version. So he did the illustrations and we did the final retouches like adding the Tan-Tári palette of colors!. We liked the result so much that we published it on our social networks and we used it as a way to invite our friends to give us support in the award ceremony.

- **Photo Contest with iGEM FCB-UANL and iGEM BIOTECH EC**

Among the collaborations, we carried out was the Photography Contest "Repercussion of climate change in Latin American communities" in partnership with iGEM FCB-UANL and iGEM BIOTECH EC, in order to raise awareness on pollution in a climate change context, based on the collective construction of a Latin American photographic memory. The details of this collaboration were explained in section 3.1 Collaboration.